

Managing irregular migration and return

A framework for understanding and measuring
pathways in and out of irregularity in the EU and
in selected Member States

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Abstract

This report builds on previous JRC work on the challenges to measure the effectiveness of returning third-country nationals (TCN) staying irregularly in the European Union (EU) to their countries of origin, particularly in light of renewed EU policy ambitions on return. It aims to fill a key evidence gap by addressing the following questions: what are the trajectories of irregular third-country nationals (TCNs) as they enter and exit the return process, and which data are available to quantify these trajectories?

The report develops a policy-oriented map of irregularity pathways, investigating: i) how the failure to fulfil the conditions for entry or stay (including after an asylum rejection) can lead to a return decision; ii) the conditions under which a return decision is issued and, in some cases suspended; and iii) the return or access to a residence permit or authorisation to stay as a way to exit irregularity.

This map is used to analyse national practices and to identify the data availability at EU and national level in five Member States: Austria, France, Germany, Italy and Spain. While the potential of EU data is currently limited to quantifying the trajectories in and out of the return process, at the national level, more information can be harvested.

The report's findings have important implications for policymakers seeking to improve the effectiveness of return and better manage irregular migration, and underscore the need for more harmonised data collection and common definitions to support evidence-based policy-making.

Executive summary

Policy context and objectives of the report

A more effective management of irregular migration and return of irregular third-country nationals (TCNs) is one of the political priorities on migration of the European Commission 2024-2029. In March 2025, the Commission published a proposal for a Regulation to establish a common return system for the return of TCNs staying irregularly in the European Union⁽¹⁾. This proposal is closely linked to the Pact on Migration and Asylum, and would repeal the Return Directive⁽²⁾, adopted in 2008. It aims to reduce the fragmentation caused by the discretion that Member States currently have in implementing return procedures, increase harmonisation, and improve data availability. The consequences of the current fragmentation and data gaps include limited EU-wide comparability and insufficient evidence to assess the effectiveness of return policy.

Previous JRC research⁽³⁾ identified the challenges in assessing return effectiveness with existing data. It

advised for a comprehensive analysis, covering not only the number of persons who return after receiving an order to leave, but also the modalities by which TCNs end up in return procedures and exit irregularity, via returns or access to residence permits

This report analyses how the existing evidence base on return can be improved, while taking into account the limited data availability at the EU level and the existing fragmentation of return policy across different national practices. It does so by pursuing three objectives:

1. To analyse the EU policy framework and data availability on irregular migration and return and to define a **map of irregularity pathways**. This map describes the different processes by which TCNs become irregularly present in the EU (*pathways into irregularity*), the processes by which they enter a return procedure as a consequence of this status, and finally a transition out of irregularity (*pathways out of irregularity*), as depicted in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1. Map of irregularity pathways - summary.

(1) Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council establishing a common system for the return of third-country nationals staying illegally in the Union, and repealing Directive 2008/115/EC of the European Parliament and the Council, Council Directive 2001/40/EC and Council Decision 2004/191/EC, Strasbourg 11.3.2025, COM(2025) 101 final.
 (2) Directive 2008/115/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on common standards and procedures in Member States for returning illegally staying third-country nationals.
 (3) Belmonte, M., Tarchi, D. and Sermi, F. (2021), How to measure the effectiveness of return, EUR 30491 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, ISBN 978-92-76-27075-1, doi:10.2760/200580, JRC122948.

2. To analyse how the map of irregularity is declined in **five different national contexts**. This analysis identifies which relevant national practices are associated with the irregularity pathways, and which data is available in Austria, France, Germany, Italy, and Spain.
3. To propose **concrete solutions** that can be implemented across Member States to improve the evidence base on return in the EU, in a context of limited data and policy harmonisation.

The report addresses policy makers and practitioners in the area of return and is based on publicly available data and information.

The fragmented policy and data landscape on irregular migration and return

The pathways in and out of irregularity are declined differently in the five Member States. The data availability at EU level is insufficient to properly quantify each pathway, yet in some cases national data can be used as a complement. The evidence gathered in this report shows that the irregularity pathways can play a significant different role across Member States, as detailed below.

1 **TCNs may become irregularly present in the EU through either unauthorised entry or by losing their lawful residence status.** In the first case, TCNs who **cross the border irregularly** may be found to be illegally present in Member States' territories. While Eurostat and Frontex data can help quantify this pathway, key limitations exist. Existing evidence shows the relevance of this pathway to irregularity varies across countries.

In the second case, **TCNs may lose their regular status due to overstaying** their visa-exempt stay, visa, or legal permit; **for having their asylum application rejected; or for having a previously granted permit revoked.** Although EU data can provide some quantitative insights into this pathway, it is subject to significant limitations, which hinders a comprehensive understanding of the issue. Identifying *overstayers* is challenging in all Member States, due to inconsistent registration and operational definitions, resulting in incomplete data. The share of *visa-exempt nationals* among TCNs found to be illegally present or ordered

to leave varies across Member States, pointing at a different role that this pathway plays.

Specifically on the loss of regular status following a *negative asylum decision*, national practices vary. Some Member States issue return decisions concurrently with the first instance rejection of an asylum application, while others delay issuance until the appeal stage, when the negative decision is confirmed. The data on negative asylum decisions and return decisions are linked only in some Member States. EU data are not linked, so it is not possible to establish whether the return decision follows an asylum rejection. Yet, as a rejected asylum application is only one of the pathways to irregular status, return decisions should outnumber negative asylum decisions. Data often contradict this expectation, as the number of unsuccessful asylum applications exceeds the number of return decisions in many cases. The proportions between orders to leave and negative asylum decisions differ across Member States, as well as across nationalities.

2 **Irregularly staying TCNs should receive a return decision stating their obligation to leave.** However, implementation varies across Member States. For example, the obligation to leave may be disconnected from the initiation of return procedures, orders to leave may be systematically issued to all TCNs found to be irregularly staying (resulting in a high volume of orders to leave), or the obligation to issue return decisions may not have a single reference in the national legal framework.

The validity period and enforceability of return decisions exhibit variations. Reasons for the suspension of return decisions, which may include asylum appeals, legal/practical barriers, or exceptional circumstances, are subject to divergent rules. Member States may suspend the enforcement of removals, while retaining the obligation to leave, through a tolerated stay status. The toleration system may cover a multiplicity of situations, and when this is the case, a significant number of persons with an obligation to leave has in fact a tolerated status. Data availability to disaggregate orders to leave is only national: while Eurostat tracks annual/quarterly orders to leave, it does not report on the stock of orders to leave, suspensions, or 'cold cases' (i.e., orders to leave issued to unreachable persons). This is a significant limitation for analysing the effectiveness of return.

3 Finally, **TCNs may exit irregularity either by returning to a third country, or by obtaining a legal status.**

As per the Directive, Member States implement different periods for voluntary departure, return counselling, pre-removal detention, and alternatives to detention to both *boost voluntary returns and prevent absconding*. However, data on these practices are incomplete. At the national level, there are different analytical categories to classify returns, thus complicating comparisons with Eurostat, and data on voluntary returns are sometimes scattered across different sources and not comprehensively available. Authorities struggle to record unassisted voluntary returns, potentially underestimating actual returns, with only few countries maintaining records of such data.

Member States implement a wide range of different approaches in cases where TCNs do not or cannot be returned for legal or practical obstacles. These include issuing of temporary *permits*, *de facto* suspending return decisions or their enforcement, and opening pathways to more stable regular status. Without an EU framework on *regularisation*, national procedures vary in permits' availability and requirements, often linked to integration, employment or humanitarian considerations. All Member States analysed have mechanisms conducive to legal status. In some cases, there are multiple regularisation permits that offer a structured access to temporary permits. While EU data is unavailable, national sources suggest that regularisations may significantly exceed the number of returns.

Potential ways forward

The proposed Regulation on a common return system aims to reduce the existing fragmentation and improve the data sharing. This is due to the

legal instrument of the Regulation, that, compared to the Directive leaves less discretion to Member States, and to specific provisions on data sharing. However, the proposed text does not address all data collection gaps highlighted in the report, negotiations will require time, and it is unlikely that the adopted text will harmonise the diverse practices currently in place in the different countries. Hence, **significant gaps in evidence and data are likely to remain.**

To address gaps in evidence and data with a more comprehensive approach to irregular migration management, **two actionable solutions** can be pursued, in line with the European Commission's ambition to digitalise return procedures:

- 1. To create national longitudinal databases**, to track TCNs' trajectories in and out of irregularity over time. These databases could be interlinked with other national databases as well as with the EU large-scale IT systems.
- 2. To develop an irregular migration and return dashboard** to consolidate all available information about pathways in and out of irregularity supporting the assessment of return effectiveness, and linking qualitative with quantitative information.

For each of these solutions, the report proposes a roadmap.

Conclusion

While the proposed Regulation aims to harmonise return procedures, significant data gaps may persist. A digitalised, evidence-based approach is critical to achieving the Commission's goals.

How to navigate this report

The report consists of five chapters that can reach high level of technical detail. Readers are invited to approach each chapter selectively based on their interests.

- 1. Chapter 1** describes the policy context, the challenges and evidence gaps in return policy, as well as the objective and research design of the report. It is a general chapter that sets the scene, recommended to **any reader**.
- 2. Chapter 2** presents the map of irregularity, designed on the basis of the policy framework and data availability at EU level (public sources). First, the Chapter clarifies the scope of the report: irregularly staying TCNs who, at some point, become known to the authorities. Second, it details each segment of the pathways in and out of irregularity, on the basis of the legal provisions in the Return Directive and data availability at EU level. The legal provisions and data availability are described in detail in the boxes. While the description of the map of irregularity is recommended to **any reader**, the boxes are recommended only to the **expert readers** interested in the legal provisions or statistical data.
- 3. Chapter 3** analyses practices and data in selected Member States – Austria, France, Germany, Italy, and Spain. The case studies concretely describe how each segment of the irregularity map is implemented as well as the EU or national data available. Each sub-chapter starts with the main take-aways section, which condenses the findings from the case studies and is recommended to **any reader**. The rest of the Chapter, as well as the relevant annexes, presents the findings from the case studies in great detail and is recommended only for **expert readers** interested in particular Member States, or in particular segments of the irregularity pathways.
- 4. Chapter 4** identifies two actionable solutions to enhance the evidence base on the management of irregular migration and return and is recommended to **any reader**. The first is the development of longitudinal and interlinked databases in Member States, modelled after the solutions implemented by the BAMF in Germany and the BFA in Austria. These databases would allow to carry out specific analysis on the effectiveness of return procedures. The second is the development of an EU irregular migration dashboard, on the basis of the revised map of irregularity that emerged from the analysis of all the case studies. The description of these two solutions is complemented by a roadmap which is recommended to **expert readers** (e.g. policymakers).
- 5. Chapter 5**, recommended to **any reader**, summarises the main conclusions from the analysis.

1. Introduction

1.1 A new policy context for return

Return is one of the political priorities of the European Commission 2024-2029. In the 2024 Political Guidelines⁽⁴⁾, the President of the Commission Ursula von der Leyen announced a new common approach to returns, including “a new legislative framework to speed up and simplify the process, ensure that returns take place in a dignified manner, digitalise case management and ensure that return decisions are mutually recognised across Europe”⁽⁵⁾. The new legislative proposal establishing a common system for the return of third-country nationals (TCNs) staying illegally in the Union (Box 1) was published in March 2025⁽⁶⁾. The chosen legislative instrument is a Regulation, which, compared to the current Return Directive, is directly applicable and reduces the discretion of the national legislator.

It is not the first time that returns feature prominently on the EU agenda. Already in 2015-2016, the large-scale arrival of third-country nationals in Europe pointed to a set of challenges in the EU and Member States’ ability to return those people who were not in need of international protection. The European Agenda on Migration, adopted by the European Commission in May 2015, already acknowledged that the EU return system was ineffective in view of the rates of successful returns of third-country nationals given an order to leave⁽⁷⁾.

Since then, **the goal of making return more effective gained political relevance and sparked intensive action by the EU institutions.** The European Commission adopted a range of measures and instruments to make full use of the legal, operational and financial instruments available. Great importance has been attached to improving cooperation with third countries on readmission⁽⁸⁾, while the role of Frontex in returns has been significantly strengthened⁽⁹⁾. On the internal dimension, a key priority was increasing the effectiveness of Member States administrative systems and return procedures. The Commission adopted the Return Handbook⁽¹⁰⁾ and two Action Plans on returns (in 2015 and 2017)⁽¹¹⁾, to encourage Member States to make full use of the provisions laid down in the 2008 Return Directive. In 2021, the Commission also adopted the EU Strategy on Voluntary Return and Reintegration to incentivise voluntary returns and improve the quality of assisted return and reintegration programmes. In addition, thanks to amendments to the Schengen Information System (SIS) adopted in 2018 and effectively implemented as of March 2023, Member States are now able to verify whether a TCN apprehended by the competent authority is already subject to a return decision issued by another Member State. The Commission called on Member States to make full use of SIS functionalities to enhance the mutual recognition of return decisions⁽¹²⁾ and to use return alerts even in cases when mutual recognition may not be possible⁽¹³⁾.

(4) Von der Leyen, U. (2024).

(5) The European Council welcomed this initiative and asked the Commission to submit a legislative proposal in October 2024. In December 2024, the Council also asked the co-legislators to advance the process (European Council 2024a, 2024b).

(6) Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council establishing a common system for the return of third-country nationals staying illegally in the Union, and repealing Directive 2008/115/EC of the European Parliament and the Council, Council Directive 2001/40/EC and Council Decision 2004/191/EC, COM(2025) 101 final.

(7) European Commission (2015a).

(8) European Commission (2021).

(9) Regulation (EU) 2019/1896 of the European Parliament and of the Council Of 13 November 2019 on the European Border and Coast Guard and repealing Regulations (EU) No 1052/2013 and (EU) 2016/1624.

(10) Commission Recommendation (EU) 2017/2338 of 16 November 2017 establishing a common ‘Return Handbook’ to be used by Member States’ competent authorities when carrying out return-related task, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32017H2338>

(11) European Commission (2015b, 2017).

(12) Commission Recommendation of 16.3.2023 on mutual recognition of return decisions and expediting returns when implementing Directive 2008/115/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council.

(13) Commission Recommendation of 23.11.2023 on cooperation between the Member States with regard to serious threats to internal security and public policy in the area without internal border controls (12(b)).

Box 1. Proposal for a Common European System for Returns

In March 2025, the European Commission published a proposal for a Regulation establishing a common system for the return of third-country nationals staying illegally in the EU. The proposal repeals the Return Directive and complements legislative instruments of the EU Pact on Migration and Asylum.

Key highlights the proposed legislation include:

- An expanded definition of ‘country of return’ (Article 4), understood as:
 - The country of origin of the TCN;
 - The country of formal habitual residence of the TCN;
 - A third country of transit towards the EU in accordance with EU or Member States readmission agreements or arrangements;
 - A third country different than the ones in points (a), (b) and (c), where the TCN has a right to enter and reside;
 - A safe third country in relation to which the application for international protection of a TCN has been rejected as inadmissible;
 - The first country of asylum in relation to which the application for international protection of a TCN has been rejected as inadmissible;
 - A third country with which there is an agreement or arrangement on the basis of which the TCN is accepted – thus allowing for the possibility of establishing ‘return hubs’.
- The Introduction of a ‘European Return Order’, to be issued jointly with national return decisions (Article 7).
- The requirement that return decisions be issued jointly with decisions ending the legal stay of TCNs (Article 7).
- Mutual recognition of return decisions, allowing Member States to enforce decisions issued by other Member States without the need to start a new process (Article 9).
- Specific provisions for the return of minors (Articles 18-20).
- Obligations for TCNs subject to return decisions to cooperate with national authorities (Articles 21-23).
- Procedural safeguards for TCNs, including the right to free legal assistance and representation during appeal processes (Article 25).
- The definition of alternatives to detention (Article 31).
- Requirement that return decisions are systematically followed up with readmission requests to the country of origin (Article 36).
- The possibility for Member States to ask for Frontex support for the enforcement of return decisions (Article 45).

The Return Directive is the main piece of the EU legislation on return. Adopted in 2008, the Directive lays down “common standards and procedures in Member States for returning irregularly staying third-country nationals”⁽¹⁴⁾ and mandates Member States to issue return decisions to any TCN staying irregularly in their territories (Chapter 2).

Previous attempts to reform the Directive had stalled. In 2018, the Commission put forward a proposal for a recast Return Directive. Its aim was to address the key challenges to effective returns by streamlining return procedures, strengthening the link between asylum and return procedures, and enhancing the effectiveness of measures to prevent absconding⁽¹⁵⁾. However, the co-legislators were unable to reach a final agreement⁽¹⁶⁾.

The current legislative impetus on return, however, is taking place against a different background. The adoption of the Pact on Migration and Asylum in 2024 marked a milestone, ending a long-standing legislative effort begun in 2016⁽¹⁷⁾. The development of ‘**efficient and fair return procedures**’ is one of the ten building blocks to implement the core obligations of the Pact, as outlined in the Common Implementation Plan⁽¹⁸⁾. The instruments linked to this building block include the Asylum Procedure Regulation⁽¹⁹⁾; the newly introduced Return Border Procedure Regulation⁽²⁰⁾; and reforms to the European Asylum Dactyloscopy Database (Eurodac), which will

become an EU-wide common migration and asylum information system⁽²¹⁾.

In addition, the Pact introduced the role of the EU Return Coordinator and a High-Level Network for Returns. The latter includes senior representatives from Member States and Schengen Associated Countries, Frontex and the EUAA⁽²²⁾. The Return Coordinator works closely with the High-Level Network, aiming to harmonise EU return policy, support its consistent implementation, and work towards the establishment of a common EU system for returns⁽²³⁾. In January 2023, the European Commission adopted its contribution to the operational strategy for effective returns. This document was informed by discussions within the High-Level Network for Returns, guided by the EU Return Coordinator, and aims to support the European Parliament and the Council in operationalising a common EU system for returns⁽²⁴⁾.

In this context, **the revision of the Return Directive stands out as a key component in the reform of the EU migration management system.** One of the main goals of the new proposed Regulation is to ensure consistent rules across Member States and to address the fragmentation of national approaches that currently exist in the management of return, which this study will explore.

.....

- (14) Directive 2008/115/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on common standards and procedures in Member States for returning illegally staying third-country nationals.
- (15) Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on common standards and procedures in Member States for returning illegally staying third-country nationals (recast), Brussels, 12.9.2018 COM(2018) 634 final.
- (16) European Parliament, Legislative Train Schedule, Proposal for a recast of the Directive on common standards and procedures in Member States for returning illegally staying third-country nationals, <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/spotlight-JD21/file-proposal-for-a-recast-of-the-return-directive>
- (17) On 6 April 2016, the Commission presented a communication entitled ‘Towards a reform of the Common European Asylum System and enhancing legal avenues to Europe’. On 4 May 2016, the Commission adopted the first package of proposals for CEAS reform with the following initiatives: a proposal for a regulation to reform the Dublin system; a proposal for a regulation to amend Eurodac and a proposal for a regulation to establish an EU Asylum Agency which is to replace the European Asylum Support Office (EASO). On 13 July 2016, the Commission put forward the second package of CEAS reform proposals: a proposal for a new regulation to replace the Asylum Procedures Directive; a proposal for a new regulation to replace the Qualification Directive; and a proposed targeted modifications of the Reception Conditions Directive.
- (18) European Commission (2024).
- (19) Which includes provisions aimed at closing gaps between the asylum and return procedures. Specifically, Article 37 established that return decisions must be issued together or without delay after an asylum rejection decision, Article 67 specifies that the appeal to these decisions must be done jointly or at least with the same timeline.
- (20) Regulation (EU) 2024/1349 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 May 2024 establishing a return border procedure, and amending Regulation (EU) 2021/1148. It set forwards a mandatory return border procedure that streamlines the return process for third-country nationals rejected in border asylum procedures.
- (21) It will store and process the biometric, identity data and other information of several categories of TCN – including asylum seekers, persons apprehended in connection with irregular border crossings, people disembarked after SAR, or who are found illegally present on a MS territory – to facilitate their identification and re-documentation, to ensure their return and readmission, and to reduce identity fraud.
- (22) European Commission. (n.d.-e).
- (23) Communication from the Commission on a New Pact on Migration and Asylum, COM(2020) 609.
- (24) European Commission (2023).

1.2 Challenges and evidence gaps in return policy

The national legislative frameworks governing the management of irregular migration and return are very diverse, making comparison across countries challenging and making it difficult to assess the effectiveness of the EU return system⁽²⁵⁾. These differences concern, for example, the link between negative asylum decisions and return decisions, the lack of a legal definition of what constitutes voluntary return, divergent approaches for assessing the risk of absconding and the use of alternatives to detention. Other aspects are also not currently established at the EU level, such as the obligation of TCNs to cooperate throughout the return process, and the range of incentives that could be employed to facilitate cooperation⁽²⁶⁾.

National differences are even stronger when it comes to non-returned persons – a phenomenon that remains significant in its magnitude and political consequences. Between 2020 and 2023, official data published by Eurostat shows that approximately less than one quarter of the persons who received an order to leave returned to a third country. In the absence of EU legislation on non-returning persons, Member States implement a wide range of different practices, from issuing temporary permits, to de facto suspending return decisions. The rights and services that this group of TCNs has access to also differ quite significantly across Member States.

The **existing data landscape mirrors the regulatory gaps at the EU level as well as the divergence in Member States’ practices. The lack of reliable data and evidence on how all steps of the return process are implemented at the Member State level** is a major challenge, and, as recognised by the Commission, renders it “difficult to pinpoint how to improve its effectiveness”⁽²⁷⁾. Data on return procedures collected at the EU level are scant and subject to

several limitations when used to analyse return and irregular migration⁽²⁸⁾.

Overall, publicly available information on the diverse national practices on return and, more in general, on the management of irregularly staying TCNs, is limited. Similarly, despite efforts at the EU level, data production remains insufficient. This generates a knowledge gap both on the **population that is subject to return procedures** and on the **different pathways** followed by those individuals. As further discussed below, this study tries to bring some evidence and contributes to bridging this knowledge gap.

1.3 Objectives and research design of the report

This report is grounded in two initial considerations: 1) an in-depth analysis of national practices is needed to fully understand return procedures; and 2) the national data landscape can provide a more nuanced account of the dynamics of return processes and, more broadly, of the situations of irregularly staying TCNs.

Building on previous JRC work on the challenges to measure return effectiveness⁽²⁹⁾, **this report aims at shedding light on the trajectories of irregular TCNs both in and out of the return process**. It does so by analysing the **policy framework and data production** at the EU level (Chapter 2) and in selected Member States (Chapter 3). It explores the different trajectories leading to an obligation to return, the statuses associated to it, and the way the selected Member States manage the process of returning irregularly staying TCNs or, otherwise, to provide alternatives to return when faced with legal or technical obstacles.

More specifically, the **main objectives** are:

1. To explore how TCNs fall into irregularity and enter the return procedure, as well as

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(25) Commission Implementing Decision establishing the 2024 thematic Schengen evaluation report ‘Bridging national gaps: towards an effective EU return system through common solutions and innovative practices, C(2024) 9171 final. Annex 2
(26) Proposal for a Directive of The European Parliament and of the Council on common standards and procedures in Member States for returning illegally staying third-country nationals (recast), Brussels, 12.9.2018 COM(2018) 634 final.
(27) European Commission (2023).
(28) Belmonte, M., Sermi, F., Tarchi, D. (2021); Siruno and Leerkes (2023).
(29) Belmonte, M., Sermi, F., Tarchi, D. (2021).

how they exit irregularity, including for TCNs subject to a return decision that are not returned.

- 2. To investigate national data collection practices**, and their alignment with data collected at the EU level, aiming to identify possible ‘dead-ends’, which prevent a more comprehensive and balanced understanding of irregular migration dynamics.
- 3. To identify**, drawing on the analysis of national practices, **alternative dimensions for measuring the management of irregular migration and return** that could integrate the ‘return rate’, which suffers from several limitations in terms of data quality and comparability⁽³⁰⁾.

To achieve these objectives, the report analyses national practices and data landscape in **five case studies (Austria, France, Germany, Italy, Spain)**. The case selection aimed at having geographical variety (with a

mix of first-entry Member States and Member States farther from the external borders), different migration situations in terms of irregular entries, the nationality composition of arrivals, asylum applications, as well as return rates. Additionally, the selected Member States display a set of institutional specificities (e.g. the level of centralisation), which are likely to be associated with a variety of approaches and data challenges on the management of irregular migration⁽³¹⁾.

The JRC commissioned five country reports providing an in-depth analysis of irregular migration and return policies and practices to academic experts in the selected Member States. The country reports, which were compiled using desk review of the literature, government and policy documents and interviews with key informants from organisations and governments, provided the starting point for the analysis. Besides the information collected for the country reports, this report relies only on publicly available information.

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(30) *ibidem*.

(31) The criteria used to narrow down the group of Member States as candidates for the case studies were: the return rate (in particular, the average difference Return Rate (as described in Belmonte, M., Sermi, F., Tarchi, D. (2021)), the number of nationalities of recipients of return decisions, the distribution of the share of the total return decisions by nationality, the institutional setting (as measured by the Decentralization Index, developed by experts for the European Committee of the Regions, to assess the degree of decentralisation between various governance structures in Member States). After a first short-list of 9 Member States, the JRC discussed with DG HOME for which countries additional research would have brought major added value, on the basis of the existing knowledge within the institution.

2. Mapping irregular migration and return processes in the EU

This **section describes the policy framework and data availability at EU level** (from public sources) on the irregularly *staying* population. The guiding questions are:

- How do third-country nationals enter an irregular stay status ('pathways into')?
- To what extent does the irregularly staying population fall under the scope of the Return Directive?
- How can third-country nationals get out of irregularity ('pathways out')?

2.1 The scope

Defining clear boundaries (both quantitatively and qualitatively) of the population that is irregularly staying in the Member States, and who then fall within the scope of EU return policy, **is a challenging endeavour**. Academic and policy-oriented research on migrant irregularity has produced a variety of typologies to account for the diversity of 'pathways' that may lead individuals to fall into a situation of irregularity. The aim of these taxonomies is often to estimate the population in an irregular situation (see Annex 1)⁽³²⁾.

In contrast, **this study seeks to trace the trajectory of the irregularly staying TCNs who may fall within the scope of EU return policy**, building on the assumption that irregular stay can both a) arise through different pathways, and b) lead to different outcomes, including, but not limited to, return. To this end, the analysis focuses on irregularly staying TCNs who, at some point, become 'known to the authorities'

and on the legal and policy mechanisms activated to address their situation. The share of the irregularly staying population who remain 'invisible' as their presence and status in the territory is never registered is thus outside the scope of this study.

The **Return Directive is taken as the reference point** to analyse the interplay between obligations and procedures emerging from EU law and those regulated at the national level. In parallel, **Eurostat's "Enforcement of Immigration Legislation" statistics** and, when relevant, **Eurostat asylum statistics**, provide the main framework against which to assess the data availability (and gaps) to quantify pathways into and out of irregularity⁽³³⁾. This approach aims to identify those dimensions of policy and legal responses in the area of irregular migration and returns, which are only partly regulated and thus captured by official EU level statistics. To shed light on those dimensions, it is necessary to dig deep into **Member States' practices and describe the specificities of national settings** (see Chapter 3).

The **green boxes** in Section 2.2 highlight the provisions of Return Directive that are relevant to define and conceptualise the trajectories in and out of irregularity of TCNs entering and staying in the Member States' territory. The **violet boxes** in Section 2.2 describe the range of data publicly available at EU level for the identified components.

2.2 The map of irregularity pathways

The Return Directive sets a general obligation for Member States to issue a return decision to any TCN staying

(32) Kraler and Ahrens (2023).

(33) Regulation (EU) 2020/851 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 June 2020 amending Regulation (EC) No 862/2007 on Community statistics on migration and international protection, OJ L 198/1, 22.6.2020; Eurostat, 'Technical Guidelines for the Data Collection under Article 5 and 7 of Regulation 851/2020 Amending Regulation 862/2007– Enforcement of Immigration Legislation (EIL) Statistics 2023 - Version 1.0'.

FIGURE 2. Map of irregularity pathways.

irregularity⁽³⁴⁾ in their territory,⁽³⁵⁾ i.e. no (longer) fulfilling the conditions of entry as set out in the Schengen Borders Code⁽³⁶⁾ or other conditions for entry, stay or residence in Member State.⁽³⁷⁾ Return decisions, either administrative or judicial, must explicitly declare the stay of the concerned third-country national as “illegal” and impose an obligation to return.⁽³⁸⁾

This section maps how TCNs can fall into irregularity and thus become subject of the scope of the Return Directive, as well as how they can enter return processes and exit irregularity. The map of the irregularity pathways emerging from the analysis of the EU policy framework consists of three main dimensions (Figure 2): 1) pathways into irregularity, 2) return processes, and 3) pathways out of irregularity.

1) Pathways into irregularity

This dimension describes the variety of processes and trajectories leading individuals to be recognised as irregularly staying in the EU territory.

This is further divided into two sub-dimensions:

a) Irregular entry. It includes the cases of people who are identified in the context of **irregular border-crossings**, as well as those who are **found to be irregularly present in a Member State’s territory following irregular entry**. Irregular stay in these cases is the failure to fulfil the conditions for regular entry as laid down in the Schengen Borders Code or in Member States’ legislation (e.g. be in possession of a valid travel document or visa) and the failure to leave the country, if refused entry or intercepted.

Box 2. Return Directive: scope

The Directive (Article 2(2)(a)) gives Member States discretion **not** to apply the Directive in the following cases:

- TCNs who have been **refused entry at the external border** in accordance with the Schengen Borders Code;
- TCNs apprehended or intercepted by the competent authorities **in connection with the irregular crossing** of Member States’ external border and who have not obtained authorisation or right to stay in the Member State.

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- (34) The European Commission favours nowadays the term ‘irregular stay’ instead of ‘illegal stay’ which was the term used in the Council Directive 2008/115/EC (Return Directive). This report adopts the term “irregular” unless referring to specific datasets, indicators or when citing of legal text.
- (35) Return Directive, Article 6(1).
- (36) Art 6 Schengen Borders Code refers to the following conditions that TCN seeking entry must fulfil: a) be in possession of a valid travel document; b) be in possession of a valid visa (except where they hold a valid residence permit or a valid long-stay visa); c) being able to justify the purpose and conditions of the intended stay, and have sufficient means of subsistence; d) not have an alert in the Schengen Information System (SIS) for the purposes of refusing entry; e) not be considered a threat to public policy, internal security, public health or the international relations of any of the Member States.
- (37) Return Directive, Article 3(2). For examples of other categories of TCN who may fall under the scope of the RD see European Commission, “Commission Recommendation (EU) 2017/2338 of 16 November 2017 establishing a common ‘Return Handbook’ to be used by Member States’ competent authorities when carrying out return-related tasks”, p. 88. These include, but are not limited to, the following categories of people: persons subject to a refusal of entry at the border, persons intercepted in connection with irregular border crossing, irregular TCN apprehended in Member States’ territory, TCNs who are holders of an expired residence permit or visa, and rejected asylum seekers.
- (38) For examples of other categories of TCN who may fall under the scope of the RD see European Commission, “Commission Recommendation (EU) 2017/2338 of 16 November 2017 establishing a common ‘Return Handbook’ to be used by Member States’ competent authorities when carrying out return-related tasks”, p. 88. These include, but are not limited to, the following categories of people: persons subject to a refusal of entry at the border, persons intercepted in connection with irregular border crossing, irregular TCN apprehended in Member States’ territory, TCN who are holders of an expired residence permit or visa, and rejected asylum seekers. The scope of situations falling within the remit of the return directive are further discussed in Section 1.4 (Analytical Framework).

Box 3. EU statistics on irregular entry

Available EU-level statistics on the above dimensions include:

- **Eurostat, third-country nationals found to be illegally present by reason, place of apprehension - annual data (rounded)** [[migr_eipre](#)]. The population covered includes TCNs who are officially found to be on the territory of a Member State and who do not fulfil, or no longer fulfil, the conditions for stay or residence in that Member State. Disaggregation by reason (grounds for apprehension) include illegal entry, which refers to irregular border-crossing and, depending on national definitions, may encompass avoiding border controls (passing between BCPs and using a fraudulent document to cross the border)⁽³⁹⁾.
- **Frontex.** Frontex collects and publishes data on the number of detections of illegal border crossings between external border crossing points, considered unauthorised at the time of the crossing under the Schengen Borders Code. This number might include persons intending to apply for asylum. The term refers to detections, rather than to persons, who might cross multiple times, and do not specify whether the person in fact entered the Member State⁽⁴⁰⁾.
- **eu-LISA, Eurodac.** Eurodac Category 2 datasets include fingerprints of TCNs, who are at least 14 years of age, who were **apprehended when irregularly crossing the external borders and who were not turned back**. Category 3 datasets include fingerprints of TCNs, who are at least 14 years of age, who were **found illegally staying in a Member State's territory**. These data are not public, but aggregated summaries can be found in eu-LISA's annual reports. These reports contain a breakdown of data for each Member State⁽⁴¹⁾. Hits between Category 3 and 2 would indicate how many TCNs found to be irregularly present entered irregularly, but i) Member States are not obliged to use the Category 3 search and Eurodac is not used systematically for this, ii) Eurodac reports do not include such hits.
- **Eurostat, third-country nationals refused entry at the external borders - annual data (rounded) by reason, by citizenship** [[migr_eirfs](#)]. These data measure refusals of entry at the *external* border (*land, sea, air*), at border crossing points. Irregular border-crossings *between* border crossing points or at the *internal* border, when border checks are temporarily reintroduced, are outside the scope, as per Eurostat guidelines.

b) Loss of regular status. This includes the case of TCNs who **overstay** their visas or permit, or who, in the case of people coming from countries **exempt from visa obligations**, have exceeded the maximum duration of stay in the Schengen area. Irrespective of the entry modality, loss of regular status may be further determined by the outcome of asylum procedures, i.e. a **rejection of**

an application for international protection. Irregularity may also occur from the expiration of other temporary authorisations to stay (e.g. on the basis of work or student permits), or when a permit is actively **revoked**. In these cases, irregular stay refers to the stay on the territory beyond the period allowed for in the residence permit, or the termination of the legal stay (Box 4).

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 (39) The category 'reason' started to be used in 2021.
 (40) Frontex (2023).
 (41) eu-LISA (2024).

Box 4. Return Directive: loss of regular status

The Return Directive aims to prevent possible losses of regular stay that is connected to the **process of renewal of a permit of stay**.

- Article 6(5) states that when the TCN staying irregularly on the territory of the Member State is in the process of renewing the residence permit or authorisation to stay, Member States **shall consider refraining from issuing a return decision until the procedure is completed**.

The Directive leaves some discretion on when to issue a return decision in the **asylum** context:

- It does not regulate **at which instance of the asylum determination process** Member States should issue a return decision, in case no other type of permit is issued.
- It does not require decisions refusing to grant international protection and return decisions to be issued **simultaneously**.
- It gives Member States **flexibility to combine return decisions with decisions terminating legal stay, removal orders, or entry bans into a single administrative act** (Article 6(6)).
- When coming into force in 2026, the Asylum Procedures Regulation (Regulation EU/2024/1348, Article 37) should eliminate any procedural gaps between the issuance of a negative decision and of a return decision, as they shall be issued in a single act, or simultaneously in two separate acts⁽⁴²⁾.

Box 5. EU statistics on persons who lost the authorisation to stay

EU-level statistics on the above dimensions include:

- **Eurostat, third-country nationals found to be illegally present by reason, place of apprehension - annual data (rounded)** [[migr_eipre](#)]. Reasons to be found illegally present include **overstay**, besides illegal entry and other reasons. Overstay includes persons who had a valid visa or residence permit, as well as asylum applicants who had been allowed to stay for the sole purpose of the asylum procedure and whose application was rejected⁽⁴³⁾ This indicator is not linked to a specific legal procedure and the Eurostat guidelines specify that if there is a national definition on the basis of which this statistics are compiled, it should be specified.
- **Eurostat, first instance and final decisions on applications by type of decision, citizenship - annual aggregated data** [[migr_asydcfst](#)]. These include a positive or negative decision on applications for international protection as well as authorisations to stay for humanitarian reasons.

(42) Regulation (EU) 2024/1348 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 May 2024 establishing a common procedure for international protection in the Union and repealing Directive 2013/32/EU.

(43) Eurostat (2023).

- **Frontex** collects monthly statistics on **illegal stay detections** reported by place of detection (inland and inland while on the move), age group, gender and top ten nationalities. However, due to different data collection approaches and data analysis methods, comparability with Eurostat data is limited.

2) Return processes

This dimension focuses on the procedures applied to individuals who stay irregularly and are **obliged to leave the territory**. TCNs who receive a return decision may be channelled through different national

procedures depending on their individual circumstances, as well as the policy in place in each Member State. A key factor to be considered here is **whether the obligation to leave is enforceable or active (i.e. not suspended), or whether it has been postponed (Box 6)**.

Box 6. Return Directive: issuance of return decisions and its suspension

The Return Directive foresees **specific cases in which the return decision may not be issued**.

- Member States can grant a permit or authorisation to stay on their territories to a person staying irregularly for **compassionate, humanitarian or other reasons** (Article 6(4)). In that case, if a return decision had been previously issued, it should be suspended or withdrawn.

The Directive establishes some specificities as regard the **issuance of a return decision when the person staying irregularly in a Member State has a connection with another Member State** (Article 6(2) and (3)). Specifically:

- When the person holds a **valid residence permit or authorisation to stay** from another Member State, the person should be required to go to the territory of that Member States. In that case, a return decision is not required, unless the TCN does not comply or his or her immediate departure is required for public policy or national security reasons.
- When the TCN staying irregularly on the territory of the Member State is **taken back by another Member States under a bilateral agreement or arrangement**, Member States may refrain from issuing a return decision.

The Directive establishes cases in which the **obligation to leave should or may be suspended** (Article 9)⁽⁴⁴⁾.

.....

(44) The Return Handbook further clarifies that “the Return Directive imposes two absolute bans: Member States are not allowed to remove a person if this would violate the principle of non-refoulement, and they are also not allowed to carry out removal for as long as suspensory effect has been granted to a pending appeal. In other cases, Member States may postpone removal for an appropriate period taking into account the specific circumstances of the individual case. The catalogue of possible reasons is open and allows Member States to react flexibly to any newly arising or newly discovered circumstances justifying postponement of removal. The concrete examples listed in the Return Directive (physical or mental state of the person concerned, technical reasons, such as lack of availability of appropriate transport facilities) are indicative examples. Member States may provide also for further cases in their national implementing legislation and/or administrative practice.”

- Removal *must* be postponed if it would violate the **principle of non-refoulement** or if suspensive effects have been granted in the context of appeal procedures (Article 9(1)),
- In addition, removal *may* be postponed following an assessment of individual circumstances linked to the third-country national's **physical or mental health** (Article 9(2)),
- Removal *may* be postponed when there are **technical obstacles for the enforcement of return** (e.g., lack of transport capacity or lack of identification) (Article 9(2)).

The Return Directive does not regulate in detail the legal status of **individuals whose return decision has been suspended or whose removal has been postponed**. However, it states that “their [of this category of people] basic conditions of subsistence should be defined according to national legislation” (recital 12). Furthermore, **in cases of postponement of removal**, Member States should guarantee as far as possible the following rights: family unity with family members present in the territory; emergency health care and essential treatment of illness; access to the basic education system for minors; special needs of vulnerable persons (Article 14).

Box 7. EU statistics on return decisions

EU-level statistics on the above dimensions include:

- **Eurostat, third-country nationals ordered to leave, and citizenship - annual and quarterly data (rounded)** [[migr_eiord](#), [migr_eiord1](#)]. These statistics describe the annually or quarterly issued orders to leave, but do not specify the reasons for issuing an order to leave and whether the order to leave is suspended. Furthermore, these statistics do not allow to identify if and in which circumstances Member States apply exceptions to the application of the Return Directive to TCNs refused entry at the border or apprehended in the context of irregular crossings. In this regard, Eurostat guidelines specify that while normally these categories do not belong to the return procedure in practice they may be included by Member States due to the specificities of administrative procedures at national level and based on national legal or administrative frameworks.
- **Frontex collects statistics on monthly return decisions issued**. These are disaggregated with the following breakdown: citizenship, gender and age group⁽⁴⁵⁾. Data by Member States is not publicly available. Due to different data collection approaches and data analysis methods, comparability with Eurostat data is limited.

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(45) Frontex (2023), Statistical Annex, Table 11.

3) Pathways out of irregular stay

This dimension refers to the options available in EU and national practices to terminate a situation of irregular stay. These options include the execution of obligations to return, either by returnees themselves

in **voluntary compliance with a return decision (voluntary return)**, or by the national authorities through the **enforcement of removal** (including through the use of coercive measures as a last resort), as well the access to a **residence permit or an authorisation to stay (Box 8)**.

Box 8. Return Directive: returns and residence permits or authorisation to stay

The Return Directive establishes two procedures to implement return: voluntary and forced return⁽⁴⁶⁾.

If no obstacles to the enforcement of the obligation to leave subsist, return decisions should allow for a period of **voluntary departure** (Article 7).

- The **period for voluntary departure** is set at between 7 and 30 days, which may be extended on a case-by-case basis.
- Member States **may refrain from granting a period of voluntary departure** in the following cases: there is a risk of absconding, if the obligation is a result of an asylum application rejected as manifestly unfounded, or if the concerned individual poses a risk to public policy, public or national security.
- **A set of measures to prevent absconding** are foreseen in the period of voluntary departure including the following: regularly reporting to authorities, financial guarantees, handing over documents, or residing in specific places. These are the same measures that can be applied in cases where return is postponed⁽⁴⁷⁾.

Following the end of the period for voluntary departure, when granted, Member States are obliged to take all necessary measures to **enforce the return decision**.

- **Removal** is defined as the enforcement of the obligation to return through the physical transportation out of the Member State and can be the subject of a separate administrative or judicial decision (i.e., separate from the return decision establishing the obligation to leave) (Article 3(5)).
- **Coercive measures** can be used to enforce removal, but should be proportionate in measure and should not exceed reasonable force (Article 8(4))⁽⁴⁸⁾.

.....

(46) The Directive states that voluntary return should be favoured (unless this would pose obstacles to the return procedure) and that Member States should provide assistance and counselling to promote voluntary return. This idea was reinforced by the 2021 'EU strategy on voluntary return and integration', which places the focus on facilitating reintegration in countries of origin, including through financial support and enhanced cooperation with third countries. See European Commission (2021b).

(47) According to Article 15 of the Return Directive, Member States can detain third-TCNs subject to return procedures only as a last resort, if less coercive measures cannot be applied, and only if there's a risk of absconding or the individual is hindering the return process. Detention should only last for a short period of time, and only continue if removal arrangements are being made with due diligence.

(48) The Directive foresees that coercive measures shall be implemented as provided for in national legislation in accordance with fundamental rights. This is in line with Article 52(1) of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, which establishes that any limitations on the exercise of the rights and freedoms recognised by the Charter must be provided for by law and respect the essence of those rights and freedoms. Subject to the principle of proportionality, limitations may be made only if they are necessary and genuinely meet objectives of general interest recognised by the Union or the need to protect the rights and freedoms of others.

The Directive envisions the possibility for Member States to grant a **residence permit or authorisation of stay to irregularly staying person on compassionate, humanitarian or other grounds**, at any time. In such cases, if the return decision has been issued, it should be either withdrawn or put on hold for as long as the residence permit or authorisation is valid (Article 6(4))⁽⁴⁹⁾.

Box 9. EU statistics on returns

EU-level statistics include:

- **Eurostat, third-country nationals returned following an order to leave - annual or quarterly data (rounded)** [[migr_eirtn](#), [migr_eirtn1](#)]
- **Eurostat, third-country nationals who have left the territory by type of return and citizenship** [[migr_eirt_vol](#)]

This set of statistics refers to the returned TCNs, who have in fact left the (national) territory following a order to leave the territory of the Member State. Disaggregation by type of return distinguishes between *forced returns and assisted voluntary returns*. According to Eurostat guidelines, unassisted voluntary returns may be included where these are reliably recorded. While according to the Return Directive, return means that the TCN is leaving the EU to a third country, for statistical purposes return also covers the movement of a person going from the reporting country back to another EU or EFTA Member State based on the enforcement of a bilateral agreement. The Guidelines specify that returns after refusals of entry are included only if the Return Directive or equivalent national legislation is implemented in these cases.

- **Frontex collects statistics on TCNs effectively returned on a monthly basis.** The following breakdown is applied: Member States, citizenship, gender, age group, country of return and type of return (voluntary, forced, TCNs returned with Frontex support). However, due to different data collection approaches and data analysis methods, comparability with Eurostat data is limited.

The next chapter analyses the management of irregular migration and return processes at the national level

against the map of irregularity pathways described above.

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(49) The Return Handbook (Commission Recommendation (EU) 2017/2338) lays down criteria that Member States that should be taken into for granting permits (13.2.Situations of protracted irregularity): the cooperative/non-cooperative attitude of the returnee, the length of factual stay of the returnee in the Member State, integration efforts made by the returnee, personal conduct of the returnee, family links, humanitarian considerations, the likelihood of return in the foreseeable future, need to avoid rewarding irregularity, impact of regularisation measures on migration pattern of prospective (irregular) migrants, likelihood of secondary movements within Schengen area.

3. Mapping of national practices and data

This section examines **pathways into and out** of irregularity and the return process as well as the **relevant data production** across the five case studies: Austria, France, Germany, Italy and Spain. When possible, statistics are presented for the cumulated period 2021–2023 to minimise comparability issues arising from different registration timing across datasets and to minimise the distortion effect of specific extreme dynamics occurring in a given year. Data are always benchmarked against the number of persons ordered to leave. In all Member States the datasets described below originate from different sources and no Member State reports data linkages across datasets. The comparison of these data is therefore aimed at assessing the order of magnitude of the phenomena they describe, rather than their precise quantification.

The analysis is structured across three key themes:

- Sub-section 3.1 describes the different pathways **into irregularity**;
- Sub-section 3.2 focuses on the **identification** of irregularly staying persons and the **issuing of orders to leave**;
- Sub-section 3.3 shifts the focus to the various processes that allow TCNs to **exit irregularity**, including by returning, but also through access to residence permits or authorisations.

Key takeaways: pathways into irregularity

Irregular stay can occur through various pathways, including irregular entry, overstaying a visa or visa-exempt period, or as a consequence of a negative decision on an asylum application.

Different definitions and analytical categories at the national level often translate into statistical reporting practices which are not reflected in EU-level statistics, affecting comparability across Member States.

Each section is divided into key takeaways and detailed analysis.

3.1 Pathways into irregularity

This section investigates the irregularity that is a consequence of an irregular entry. It analyses practices and data related to the identification of irregularly staying TCNs in connection to an irregular entry (Section 3.1.1.1), and ii) the quantification of irregularly staying TCNs who entered irregularly (Section 3.1.1.2).

It answers to the following questions:

- Are TCNs who irregularly cross (or try to cross) the border subject of a return decision? To what extent is this consistent across Member States?
- What are the practices that Member States implement to reduce the risks that TCNs end up staying irregularly on the territory, after an irregular entry?

To what extent the persons who entered irregularly end up staying irregularly? And what EU and national data exist to quantify this phenomenon?

Irregularity after an irregular entry:

- In none of the Member States analysed being refused entry at the border or being apprehended in the proximity of the border leads to issuing a return decision.
- Data collected at the EU level on number of persons found to be illegally present shows that the irregular entry pathway plays a different role across the five Member States. While significant in Italy and Germany, it appears to be less relevant in France. In Spain,

none of the persons found to be illegally present are recorded as entering irregularly, despite the country's location, suggesting differences in definitions used at the national level.

Irregularity after a regular entry or stay:

- The identification of irregular stay as a consequence of overstaying the period of authorised stay (on a Schengen or national visa, on a permit, or as visa-waived stay) is challenging. Although at the moment not fully exploited, VIS offers opportunities in this respect, as will do EES once operational.
- Currently, the absence of robust registration methods on overstayers and common operational definitions is reflected in the incomplete data landscape. Eurostat's collection on TCNs found to be illegally present due to overstay can be used as a proxy, however, the numbers are only partially reliable.
- Data on visa-exempt nationalities provides some insights into a subset of persons identified as irregularly staying which can be assumed to have entered legally. The proportion of visa-exempt nationals amongst irregularly staying persons is significant, representing in some cases 1 in 3 or 1 in 4 of the total. This however varies across Member States and according to the metric used: Spain and Germany record the highest rates of visa-exempt nationals among the persons found to be illegally present (between 2021-2023, 30% and 21%, respectively). In the case of persons who are issued return decisions, Germany has the highest share of visa-exempt nationals (31%), followed by Italy (25%) and Spain (21%).
- The identification of irregular stay after a rejected asylum application is in principle easier, as the irregular stay is linked to an active action by the authorities terminating the authorised stay.
- However, comparisons across countries should consider the differences in national practices in relation to return following an unsuccessful asylum procedure, with only some Member States currently issuing decisions together with a first-instance rejection and others waiting for a confirmation of the rejection at the appeal stage.

- EU-level information on the number of unsuccessful asylum applicants receiving orders to leave or found to be illegally present is not available. The relevant Eurostat datasets can nonetheless be compared to quantify the size of the two population groups.
- In all Member States, asylum rejections at first or final instance are lower than persons found to be illegally present suggesting that unsuccessful asylum procedures represent a relatively smaller pathway into irregular stay.
- The number of return decisions should in principle be larger than asylum rejections at first or final instance depending on the national legislation. This is because the asylum pathway into irregularity is only one of the possible pathways. However, data is not always coherent with this. Furthermore, in Member States where return decisions are issued simultaneously with negative asylum decisions (e.g., Italy and Germany), data suggests that a number of unsuccessful applicants do not receive return decisions.
- Final negative decisions in appeal or review are smaller than persons ordered to leave in all Member States except Germany. This is compatible with the hypothesis that a large number of the applications rejected at final instance receive a return decision and that the loss of the right to stay after receiving a negative decision at final instance, when no other authorisation is granted, represents a relatively small pathway towards the order to leave⁽⁵⁰⁾.
- Member States differ in the relationship between the number of asylum rejections and irregular stay (as in found to be irregularly present or ordered to leave). While in the period 2021-2023, found to be irregularly present is the larger indicator in all Member States except in France, negative decisions at first instance are higher than orders to leave in Spain, Italy, and Germany, while lower in Austria and France.
- Importantly, the relationship identified at the aggregate level in the Member State between the number of asylum rejections and orders to leave are not preserved when looking at individual nationalities within Member States. At the same time, the same nationalities present different patterns across Member States.

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(50) It is unclear whether, in Member States where return decisions are issued simultaneously with first-instance negative decisions, a new return decision is issued following a negative final-instance decision, or if the previously suspended return decision is "reactivated".

3.1.1 Third-country nationals who do not fulfil conditions of entry

To **prevent irregular entries, Member States refuse entry to TCNs** who do not fulfil the conditions of entry at the external, or, if temporarily reinstated, internal border crossing points. Similarly, they apply

different procedures in the proximity of the border. As these practices in fact prevent irregularity, they are not considered pathways in themselves⁽⁵¹⁾. Yet, since Member States have the discretion to apply the Directive in these cases (Box 2), they are described in Box 10.

Box 10. Refused entry at the border or its proximity

TCNs who attempt to cross the border at the border crossing point, who do not fulfil the conditions of entry, for reasons like absence of valid travel documents or valid visa, or lack of sufficient means of subsistence, and who do not intend to apply for asylum are refused entry. The refusal of entry at the border is regulated by the Schengen Borders Code, for both the external borders, and for the internal border in cases of temporary reintroduction of internal border controls. The person refused entry shall not be allowed to enter the territory. While an appeal is possible, this does not have suspensive effect on the refusal of entry, which should be recorded by border guard authorities.

TCNs who enter irregularly the internal or external border may also be **apprehended in its proximity**. They may be sent by the authorities directly back to the country they were coming from before crossing the border. This often happens in the context of bilateral agreements between Member States.

- In **Italy**, “deferred refusal of entry” (respingimento con accompagnamento alla frontiera) includes persons apprehended in proximity to the border, or persons temporarily admitted to the country, for example following a rescue operation.
- In **Germany**, removals in proximity to the border (Zurückschiebung) refer to expedited procedures in proximity of the border, in cases when another Member State takes the TCN back on the basis of intergovernmental agreements or the Dublin Regulation.
- In **Austria**, “Zurückschiebung” refers to the return of an individual to another EU Member State when he or she enters the country irregularly and is apprehended within 14 days.
- **France** uses simplified readmissions (réadmissions simplifiées or remises frontalières) for apprehensions in proximity of an internal land border. This enables the immediate transfer of the apprehended individual to the border authorities of the Schengen state from which they arrived and with which France has signed a readmission agreement.
- In **Spain**, the legislation establishes an expedited procedure for summary returns (devoluciones), applied to persons identified entering Spain irregularly or violating an entry ban.

None of the five Member States applies the Directive to refusals of entry at the border or in its proximity.

Refusals of entry at the *external border* are collected by Eurostat (Box 3). Some national sources provide data on refusals of entry at the *internal border*, in cases of temporary reintroduction of border controls, and on refused entry in the *proximity of the borders*.

.....

(51) See also Section 2.1 Border cases of the Annex to the Return Handbook (European Commission 2017, b).

- In Germany, parliamentary enquiries publish the number of persons refused entry at the border (Zurückweisung), including internal and external, as well as on persons removed in proximity of the border (Zurückschiebung). No information is available on whether the person leaves the Member States or end up staying in the country. Germany also provides police crime statistics that report the number of crimes on attempts of irregular entry. Crime statistics refer to offences rather than persons and do not specify why the attempt was not successful.
- In France, a recent report of the Court of Auditors published data on refusals of entry based on annual reports by the Direction Générale des Étrangers en France (DGEF) and Direction Nationale de la Police aux Frontiers (DNPAF).

TCNs crossing the border irregularly and who are not refused entry **may transition into an irregular stay**⁽⁵²⁾. It is hard to comprehensively quantify the phenomenon of irregular entry. Frontex data are insufficient as they cover detections rather than persons, refer to illegal crossing between external border crossing points only, and are not informative on whether the person concerned is still in the Member State. Eurodac data on hits between persons found to be irregularly present (Category 3) and who irregularly crossed the border are not available (Category 2) (Box 3). Eurostat data on TCNs found to be illegally present report irregular entry among the reasons for the irregularity and are the only source of data available at the EU level, yet seem to be only partially reliable (Figure 3).

- In **Italy**, nearly all cases of TCNs found to be illegally present during 2021-2023 were attributed to irregular entries (99% of cases, on average), while in **Germany** approximately one-third of such cases were attributed to irregular entries. Since the number of orders to leave is smaller than TCNs found to be irregularly present after an irregular entry, it could be interpreted that only **a fraction** (57% in Germany and 16% in Italy) of people irregularly staying after an irregular entry **received a return decision**.
- On the contrary, during the period 2021-2023, **France** reported only a small percentage of persons found to be illegally present due to an irregular entry (averaging 5%). The gap in magnitude with orders to leave suggests that **irregular entry may**

not be the most important pathway towards irregular stay.

- In **Spain**, the totality of persons found to be illegally staying are recorded as overstayers, while none is recorded as illegally present due to an irregular entry (see Section 3.1.2.2). Given that Spain lies along two migratory routes (Western Mediterranean and Atlantic routes) for irregular entry, the fact that **none is recorded as illegally staying after irregular entry** suggests that a different definition applies.⁽⁵³⁾
- Finally, in **Austria**, no information is available on persons found to be irregularly present after an irregular entry.

Finally, national sources may provide data on irregular entries.

- In **Germany**, for instance, annual crime statistics report irregular entries⁽⁵⁴⁾. The data includes as a subset ‘attempts of irregular entry’. It is not clear whether the cases not recorded as “attempts” refer to persons who ended up staying in the country (Box 11).
- In **Austria**, situation reports by the Federal Crime Police Office includes data on “persons who have entered or are staying unlawfully” which includes persons denied entry at the border, together with persons found to be irregularly present within Austrian territory, and those issued an entry ban (BMI II / Bundeskriminalamt, 2023).

.....

(52) There are cases where irregular entry does not translate into irregular stay. According to the Schengen Borders Code, applicants for international protection, for instance, have a right to remain in Member States territory during the processing of their applications, even if this does not constitute an entitlement to a residence permit (Article 9, Asylum Procedures Directive). The Asylum Procedures Regulation, to be implemented as of June 2026, maintains this provision for applications channelled through the administrative procedure, and introduces a border procedure for applications made following apprehensions in connection to unauthorised border-crossings.

(53) As mentioned in Box 4, “this indicator is not linked to a specific legal procedure and the Eurostat guidelines specify that if there is a national definition on the basis of which these statistics are compiled, it should be specified”.

(54) Website of the Federal police with the crime Statistics: https://www.bka.de/EN/CurrentInformation/Statistics/PoliceCrimeStatistics/policecrimestatistics_node.html

FIGURE 3. TCNs found to be illegally present after irregular entry, and TCNs ordered to leave, cumulated period 2021–2023.

Source: Eurostat, migr_eipre, migr_eiord. Note: for Austria data on found to be illegally present after irregular entry are missing. For Germany, the data covers the period 2022–2023 as disaggregated data for persons found to be illegally present were missing for 2021.

Box 11. National data on irregular entries, Germany

In Germany, the following national data are available to complement the Eurostat statistics described above:

- **unauthorised entries** (including attempts, as a sub-category) from the police annual crime statistics, that record cases rather than persons (and one person may be involved in multiple attempted entries for instance);
- **refusals of entry** (including at the internal border) (Zurückweisung) and **removals in the proximity of the border** (Zurückschiebung) from Parliamentary enquiries.

As shown in Figure 4, the comparison of national data with Eurostat’s refusals of entry at the external border suggests that the vast majority of refusals of entry happens at the internal border (77%).

Comparing the data on attempts of unauthorised entry with total unauthorised entry suggests that the majority (73%) of entries was successful, even if intercepted by the police at the border.

Removals in the proximity of the border, although small compared to refusals of entry, are not negligible if compared to other indicators.

FIGURE 4. National and EU data on irregular entries: unauthorised entry from crime statistics, refusals of entry at any border, refusals of entry at the external border, removals in the proximity of the border, 2022.

Source: JRC elaboration on national police crime statistics, data from Parliamentary enquiries, and Eurostat [migr_eirfs].

Note: The bars reporting crime statistics are dashed because the data refer to cases rather the persons, and the person can be involved in multiple entries (or attempted thereof).

National police statistics provide also annual data on crimes related to **irregular stay after irregular entry**. Comparing this number to Eurostat’s found to be illegally present after an irregular entry, some differences emerge. In 2022, the police crime statistics reported 108,000 offences of irregular stays following irregular entry. In contrast, the data submitted to Eurostat reports a significantly lower number, with 65,410 persons found to be illegally present due to irregular entry (Figure 5). These differences may be attributed to different collection practices and definitions. One important difference is that national data focuses on offenses reported to the police⁽⁵⁵⁾, rather than on persons found to be illegally present.

FIGURE 5. Persons found to be illegally present due to irregular entry in Germany in national and Eurostat data, 2022.

Source: JRC elaboration based on Eurostat [migr_eipre] and police crime statistics.

Note: The bars reporting crime statistics are dashed because the data refer to cases rather the persons, and the person can be involved in multiple entries (or attempted thereof).

(55) According to website of the Federal Criminal Police Office, these statistics “contain only those offences which have come to police attention, been processed by the police and, before compilation begins, passed to the public prosecutor’s office”, Federal Criminal Police Office (2023).

3.1.2 Third-country nationals who no longer fulfil conditions of entry or stay

This section investigates irregularity as a consequence of a change in status in what previously was a regular stay. It analyses irregularly staying TCNs from countries exempt from visa obligations, overstayers, and unsuccessful international protection applicants, regardless of their regular or irregular entry to a Member State’s territory:

By looking at the practices and data, the guiding questions are:

- To what extent did third-country nationals who are irregularly staying in the country or who receive a return decision entered the Member State regularly and overstayed?
- To what extent do rejected asylum applicants receive a return decision?

3.1.2.1 Overstay when a Schengen visa is not required

The European Union currently maintains a **visa-exempt regime** with a number of third countries⁽⁵⁶⁾, which allows for short stays in the Schengen area without the need to obtain a Schengen visa, provided citizens of these countries hold a valid biometric passport. There are no specific national practices in this area, as the list of visa-exempt countries is regulated at the EU level.

Any dataset describing irregularity that provides a nationality disaggregation can be broken down into the group of TCNs that require a visa and the group of TCNs that do not require a visa. Assuming that TCNs who do not require a visa have entered the EU regularly, it is possible to estimate the number of persons found to be irregularly present or who received a return decision overstaying the maximum permitted visa-exempt period.

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(56) The visa-exempt regime includes citizens from two special administrative regions of China (Hong Kong and Macao) and one territorial authority not recognized as a state by at least one EU member state (Taiwan). For a full list, see: European Council (n.d.), EU visa agreements with non-EU countries, <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/infographics/eu-visa-agreements-with-non-eu-countries/#0>

The visa-exempt pathway into irregularity is significant, although differences emerge across Member States and across metrics used to measure the irregularly staying population:

- When using ‘persons receiving an order to leave’ (OTL) and ‘persons found to be irregularly present’ as metrics for irregular stay, **the proportion of visa-exempt nationals receiving an OTL is higher than the proportion of visa-exempt nationals found to be illegally present** in all cases except Spain (Figure 6). This may signal that it is more likely to initiate a return procedure for nationals from visa exempt countries who stay irregularly, than for nationals who require a visa.
- **The visa-exempt pathway appears to be more important in Spain and Germany, than in France and Austria, while for Italy it depends on the metric used.** More specifically, Spain and Germany report the largest proportions of visa exempt nationals amongst individuals found to be illegally present during the period 2021-2023 (at 29.6% and 21%, respectively). The proportion is smaller in France (9%), Italy (7%), and Austria (6.7%). A slightly different picture emerges when examining the proportion of visa-exempt nationals among TCNs ordered to leave. Germany has the highest share of visa-exempt nationals, at 31%, followed closely by Italy (25%) and Spain (21%). France and Austria, on the other hand, report lower proportions, with 13% of TCNs ordered to leave being visa-exempt nationals. The vast majority of visa-exempt third country nationals found to be irregular present or ordered to leave in Spain is composed of Latin America nationals, while in Germany of Western Balkans and Ukrainian nationals. In Italy, the main nationalities of visa-exempt TCNs found to be irregularly present or ordered to leave are from Western Balkan countries (Albania, Serbia), as well as from Latin American countries (Peru, Colombia, Brazil), Moldova, Ukraine and Georgia.

FIGURE 6. Proportion of third-country nationals ordered to leave and found to be illegally present who are visa-exempt, 2021-2023.

Source: JRC elaboration based on Eurostat [migr_eipre] and [migr_eiord].

3.1.2.2 Overstay after a visa or residence permit

TCNs who do not fall under the visa-exempt regime (or do not own a biometric passport) and TCNs who apply for long-term stay require a visa or a residence permit. No significant national practices have been found to minimise the transition from authorised stay on a Schengen or national visa, or permit, to unauthorised stay visa.

Currently, **methods to quantify visa or permit overstayers at EU and national level do not exist.** The Visa Information System could be used to gain more insights on this trajectory into irregular stay (in particular of asylum applicants), but its current use is limited. The Entry-Exit System, once operational, could improve the evidence base on overstay (Box 12).

The absence of robust registration methods on overstayers and of common operational definitions is reflected in the incomplete data landscape. Eurostat’s collection on TCNs found to be illegally present due to overstay can be used as a

proxy. However: 1) the indicator is intended to capture under a single category overstayers of valid visa or residence permits together with asylum applicants (as per technical guidelines - Box 5); 2) the numbers are only partially reliable since some Member States report 100% or 0% of the data under one category.

- In **Spain**, data reported to Eurostat since 2021 suggests that all identified irregular TCNs were, in fact, overstayers. However, this assumption may not be entirely realistic, as it is unlikely that every single irregular migrant in Spain has overstayed their visa or residence permit, or is a rejected asylum applicant (see above).
- In **Italy**, overstayers account for less than 1% of the total number of TCNs found to be irregularly present in both 2022 and 2023, a remarkably low proportion; while in Germany the reported figure is consistently 0, with the majority of reasons being attributed to illegal entry (approximately one-third of the cumulated total) and ‘Other’ (approximately two-thirds of the cumulated total)⁽⁵⁷⁾.

(57) The national metadata did not provide additional information to explain why the overstay category is zero.

- In **France**, overstay makes up only a small fraction of individuals found to be illegally present, ranging from 1.5% in 2021 to 3.6% in 2023, while the majority are categorised under ‘Other’.
- **Austria** does not consistently provide disaggregated data over time.

At the national level, data shows a varied picture on the significance of the overstay pathway (either from visa, permit, or a visa-exempt period) into irregularity.

- In **Spain**, there is an analytical distinction for cases of third-country nationals who held a residence permit and subsequently fell into irregularity (‘supervening irregularity’ or *irregularidad sobrevinida*) and those

who never held a residence permit (‘profound irregularity’ or *irregularidad profunda*). The latter, however, may include TCNs who overstayed a tourist visa⁽⁵⁸⁾. Statistics from the Permanent Observatory on Immigration - OPI⁽⁵⁹⁾ on persons granted temporary residence authorisations (see Section 3.3.2) includes a disaggregation on whether their irregular status was of the supervening or profound type. While supervening irregularity coincides with the definition of permit overstay, the fact that short-term visa overstays may be included within profound irregularity renders an accurate estimate of all overstayers more difficult. Between December 2020 and December 2023, 93% of all temporary residence authorisations were granted to persons who were in profound irregularity, which seemingly contrasts with data communicated to Eurostat on persons found to be illegally present.

Box 12. Data on visas and overstayers; the Visa Information System (VIS) and the Entry-Exit System (EES).

The **Visa Information System (VIS)** is a centralised database that allows Schengen States to share visa data, in particular data on decisions relating to short-stay visa applications. However, VIS data does not provide sufficient information to track overstayers.

VIS can be used by national asylum authorities in the context of the Dublin procedure for determining the Member State responsible for examining an asylum application. Asylum related searches in VIS would be able to identify how many asylum applicants had previously obtained a Schengen visa from EU Member States. Nevertheless, VIS reports lack detailed information on the issuing Member State, and it is unclear whether search results remain linked to the asylum application in cases where Dublin criteria do not apply. This limits the ability to track rejected applicants who initially entered the Schengen area with a valid visa.

Additionally, while data on visas issued each year and on residence permits are publicly available (DG HOME and ESTAT), they do not contain information on the exit of the person from the EU when the permit or visa expired, nor on permit renewals. As a result, these datasets are of limited use for quantifying irregularity following regular entry.

In contrast, the upcoming **Entry-Exit System (EES)**, scheduled to launch in 2025, promises to provide more comprehensive data on entries and exits of non-EU travellers at external borders, regardless of whether a short-stay visa is required. The EES will automatically calculate authorised stay periods and alert EU Member States when stays expire. This will enable the quantification of overstayers and, depending on the system’s integration with other datasets, shed light on the number of individuals staying irregularly in EU countries, including rejected asylum applicants who entered with a valid visa.

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(58) Martín, D.G (2024), Preparatory Analysis for Spain; Ministerio de Inclusion, Seguridad Social y Migraciones (2021)

(59) See: Ministerio de Inclusión, Seguridad Social y Migraciones. Observatorio Permanente de la Inmigración (n.d.) Personas con autorizacion de residencia por arraigo, at <https://www.inclusion.gob.es/web/opi/estadisticas/catalogo/arraigo?tab=resultados>

- **German** police crime statistics provide a breakdown of irregular stay cases, distinguishing between those who entered the country irregularly and those who did not. It can be inferred that individuals without irregular entry likely entered the country through regular channels (either *visa-exempt* or *visa required*). In both 2022 and 2023, the proportion of persons staying irregularly who seemingly entered the country regularly was significant, respectively 22 and 25%⁽⁶⁰⁾.

3.1.2.3 Overstay after unsuccessful asylum applications

Rejected asylum applicants no longer fulfil the conditions to stay, and may hence **transition to an irregular status if they fail to leave Member States' territories**. The irregular status may be prevented by appealing the first-instance asylum decision. The impact of an appeal on the return process depends on the national legislation governing at which instance return decisions are issued, and whether appeals have suspensory effects. The **appeal** potentially gives access to another temporary authorisation to stay until the final decision is issued⁽⁶¹⁾.

Compared to the other categories of irregularly staying third-country nationals described in this section, rejected asylum applicants are a group of persons transitioning to an irregularly stay which are more easily identifiable by the authorities. While authorities may lose track of overstayers, rejected asylum applicants who do not abscond are known to the authorities which assessed their applications. The termination of their legal stay is sanctioned by an 'active' act by the authority (the asylum decision), rather than 'automatically' occurring due to expiration of the authorised stay period. For this reason, it should be in principle easier to identify rejected asylum applicants as irregularly staying and to issue return decisions when the conditions of stay are no longer fulfilled.

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(60) The terminology of the crime statistics is: unauthorised stay without unauthorised entry (border crossing). This category, along with 'unauthorised stay after unauthorised/uncleared entry (border crossing) makes up the unauthorised stay according to Section 95(1) nos. 1 and 2 of the Residence Act.

(61) Applicants who do not qualify for international protection, may be able to access national forms of protection (e.g. humanitarian permits), hence receiving a positive decision on their application.

(62) EMN Spain (2018)

(63) The new law on immigration of 2024 contains a clear reference to the fact that a negative decision of the CNDA (second instance) should be followed by the issuance of an order to leave. It imposes a decision to the Prefects to issue an order to leave after a negative decision in second instance. See: Law n. 2024-42 of 26 January 2024 for managing immigration, improving integration; Service Public (2024).

(64) Eurostat data on rejection covers rejections for both international and national protection statuses.

Member States differ as to when a negative asylum decision translates into a return decision; and which authorities are responsible to issue a return decision:

- **In Spain and France, return decisions are not issued jointly with decisions rejecting applications for international protection at first instance, and do not fall under the remit of national asylum authorities.**

- In **Spain**, return decisions are separate from negative decisions on asylum applications (and from any other decisions ending the legal residency of a third-country national). Return decisions fall under the responsibility of the National Police, while the Spanish Asylum Office – OAR is responsible for processing applications for international protection⁽⁶²⁾.

- In **France**, return decisions are issued by Prefectures. They follow negative asylum decisions at first instance only when applicants are from safe countries of origin, whereas in all other cases issuance of an order to leave takes place only after a second-instance rejection⁽⁶³⁾.

- **In Italy, Austria and Germany return decisions are issued alongside first instance rejections** and by the same authority (the Territorial Commissions for the Recognition of International Protection for Italy, the Federal Office for Immigration and Asylum (BFA) for Austria, and the Federal Office for Migration and Refugees (BAMF) for Germany).

By comparing **Eurostat data on asylum rejections**⁽⁶⁴⁾ at first and second instance with data on **persons found to be irregularly present, and persons ordered to leave**, we can gain further insights into the weight that the asylum inflow has on persons issued return decisions in these Member States (Figure 7). In principle,

FIGURE 7. Asylum rejections at first and final instance, persons found to be illegally present, and orders to leave (OTL), in the period 2021-2023, by Member State.

Source: Eurostat [migr_eipre], [migr_asydcfst], [migr_asydcfina], [migr_eiord].

the number of orders to leave should be higher than the number of rejected asylum applicants, as the loss of legal stay due to asylum negative decision is only one pathway towards irregular stay⁽⁶⁵⁾.

- In **all Member States but France** the number of **persons found to be irregularly present**, irrespective of the legal procedure that led to this identification, **is the largest indicator among those signalling irregularity**. This is consistent with the fact that asylum is only one pathway towards irregularity and that not all persons found to be irregularly present receive an order to leave.
- In **Germany, Italy** and **Spain**, rejected applications for international protection at **first instance are higher than the number of persons ordered to leave**. In Germany, this difference is particularly important, with asylum rejections being 187% of the number of persons ordered to leave, whilst in Spain and Italy these are 115% and 113% higher (Figure 8). This is particularly striking in the German and Italian case, given that according to national legislation, orders to leave should be issued simultaneously with negative decisions, even if they may be suspended

later on. This suggests that not all rejected asylum applicants (for international and national protection) are issued an order to leave.

- In contrast, in **France** and **Austria negative decisions at first instance** between 2021-2023 **have been lower than the number of persons issued return decisions** (representing respectively 72% and 81% of OTLs), which suggests that a high proportion of rejected asylum applicants effectively receive a return decision (although in France return decisions are normally issued only at final instance).
- When it comes to **final decisions in appeal or review, in all Member States except Germany, rejections are smaller than persons ordered to leave**. This suggests that a large number of the applications rejected at final instance receive a return decision. It also suggests that, except for Germany, the loss in the right to stay linked to a negative decision at final instance represents a relatively small pathway into irregular stay. Furthermore, in all Member States, negative decisions at first or final instance are significantly outnumbered by the number of persons found to be illegally present⁽⁶⁶⁾.

(65) Since return decisions are not issued simultaneously with negative asylum decisions in all Member States, persons ordered to leave may have received a negative decision in a different year, making it challenging to establish a direct correlation between the two datasets in a single year. This is why the cumulated 2021-2023 period is considered.

(66) It is unclear whether, in Member States where return decisions are issued simultaneously with first-instance negative decisions, a new return decision is issued following a negative final-instance decision, or if the previously suspended return decision is “reactivated”.

When looking at the numbers by nationality of applicants, the patterns observed at the aggregate level disappear and differences emerge both within countries and for the same nationality across countries (Box 13).

FIGURE 8. Proportions between negative decisions at first or final instance and TCNs ordered to leave, or persons found to be illegally present, 2021-2023.

Source: own calculation on Eurostat [migr_eiord]; [migr_asydcfsta]; [migr_asydcfina].

Note: the black dashed line represents 100%, when the value of the indicator at the numerator is equal to the one at denominator.

Box 13. Asylum rejections and orders to leave by selected nationalities across five Member States.

The table below shows the ratios between first instance rejections and orders to leave, for the most important nationalities in the Member States in the period 2021-2023⁽⁶⁷⁾. Differences emerge within and across countries.

For instance, citizens from **Pakistan, Georgia** and **Morocco** feature among the most important⁽⁶⁸⁾ nationalities in first-instance asylum rejections or orders to leave in all five Member States. The ratios between first-instance rejections and OTL registered in each Member States differ from the pattern observed at aggregate level and across Member States. In particular:

- The number of negative asylum decisions given to Pakistani citizens is far higher than the number of orders to leave in Italy (714%), Spain (502%) and Germany (201%); almost equal to the number of orders to leave in Austria (99%); smaller in France (83%).
- The number of negative asylum decisions given to Georgian citizens is far higher than the number of orders to leave in all countries except Austria, ranging from 391% (Spain) to 120% (Austria). In Austria, negative decisions represent only 42% of orders to leave.

(67) The importance is defined as being in the top 80% for first instance rejections or orders to leave.

(68) This is conventionally defined using the following criterion: a nationality features in the group of the ranked nationalities making 80% of the total indicator (OTL or first-instance rejections), in the 2021-2023 period.

- The number of negative asylum decisions given to Moroccan citizens is far smaller than the number of orders to leave in all countries except Austria, ranging from 6% (France) to 64% (Germany). In Austria, negative decisions are as many as orders to leave. .

TABLE 1. Ratios between first instance rejections and orders to leave for selected nationalities in the period 2021-2023, by Member State

	Austria	France	Germany	Italy	Spain
Afghanistan	77%	170%	55%		
Albania		78%	74%	8%	
Algeria		5%	64%	13%	10%
Armenia		103%			
Bangladesh	75%	144%		666%	
Bosnia and Herzego..			197%		
Cameroon		63%			
China				27%	
Colombia					466%
Comoros		368%			
Côte d'Ivoire		111%		559%	23%
Democratic Republic..		180%			
Egypt	86%	28%		214%	
El Salvador					863%
Georgia	42%	120%	221%	150%	391%
Guinea		115%			62%
Haiti		817%			
Honduras					412%
India	105%	22%	87%	39%	
Iran		17%	504%	4%	
Iraq	52%	20%	322%		
Mali		51%			7%
Mauritania		149%			
Moldova		48%	201%	15%	
Morocco	103%	6%	64%	13%	32%
Nicaragua					287%
Nigeria		169%	314%	241%	
North Macedonia			330%		
Pakistan	99%	83%	201%	714%	502%
Peru				106%	427%
Russia		188%	134%		
Senegal		44%		101%	32%
Serbia	4%		160%		
Somalia		209%	265%		
Sri Lanka		144%			
Sudan		89%			
Syria			254%		
The Gambia		3%		185%	30%
Tunisia	99%		80%	53%	
Türkiye	57%	187%	351%		
Ukraine		155%	24%		
Venezuela			572%		487%
Vietnam			95%		

Note: The size of the bubble represents the ratio in percentage. Colours indicate positive ratios, whereby first-instance rejections are larger than orders to leave (orange), and negative ratios, whereby first-instance rejections are smaller than orders to leave (blue).

In some cases, **national sources** provide additional information to quantify pathways towards irregularity:

- In **Germany** a Parliamentary enquiry⁽⁶⁹⁾ reports the number of persons with an obligation to leave at a given point in time (30 June 2023) with a

negative asylum decision. Out of 270,098 persons with an obligation to leave, 169,907 (i.e. 61%) had a negative asylum decision⁽⁷⁰⁾. This is consistent with the observation that asylum rejection is a significant pathway into irregularity, yet other pathways also play an important role. The share of persons with an

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(69) Deutscher Bundestag (2023a).

(70) The level of instance for the asylum decision is not specified. However, it should be noted that the Central Register for Foreigners (AZR), that is the source used to provide this information, until recently recorded only the final asylum decision when the obligation to leave came into force. Currently, it records both the first and final instance decisions (source: written exchange with BAMF).

order to leave as well as a negative asylum decision varies by nationality. Looking at the nationalities for which data are provided (top 15), the shares range from 49% in the case of Turkish nationals, to 80% in the case of Iraqi nationals (Annex 4).

- In **France**, the Court of Auditors reports that, in the period 2019-2022, 28% of orders to leave were due to the rejection of an asylum application. Other reasons include the refusal of residence permits (22%), being found irregularly staying by the police (39%) and public order related issues (5%)⁽⁷¹⁾. This is consistent with the observation above that in France the asylum pathway seems comparatively less significant.
- In **Austria**, the Court of Auditors publishes data on measures to terminate the stay of the person in the context of the asylum procedure and outside. Numbers covering 2016-2017 suggest that around 80% of status termination measures are taken in the context of asylum procedures, thus confirming the significance of the asylum pathway into irregularity⁽⁷²⁾.

3.2 Being identified as irregularly staying

When a third-country national is issued a return decision, he or she is identified as irregularly staying and becomes subject to an obligation to leave. **This obligation, however, has various enforceability statuses, that may change over time.** Persons

issued a return decision may decide to lodge an appeal against it, which could carry suspensive effect; or there may be legal or practical obstacles to their return, for example, on non-refoulement grounds thus suspending the removal.

This means that **the number of persons with an “active” obligation to leave at a given point in time (stock) cannot be estimated by looking at the variation of return decisions over time (net inflow) and actual returns (outflow).**

The sections below analyse how obligations to leave are implemented in the five Member States, their enforceability, the measures taken when obstacles to their execution arise, and the relevant data production. The guiding questions, whose answers are summarised in the ‘Key takeaways’ Section, are:

- Which national practices correspond to return decisions, which cases do they cover, and how are they recorded in national data?
- When are the return decisions suspended, on which grounds, and how are suspensions recorded in the national data, if at all?
- Which practices do Member State implement to minimise the risk of absconding after a return decision? How many TCNs absconded after receiving an order to leave?

Key takeaways: being identified as irregularly staying

- The Return Directive imposes an obligation on Member States to issue return decisions to TCNs identified as irregularly staying within their territories, but this obligation is implemented in different ways across Member States. In particular, the act whereby the authorities lay down the obligation to leave is not necessarily the same as (or followed by) the act that starts the return procedure (as in the case of Spain).

- The different legal categories at the national level make it difficult to pin down which cases are covered by Eurostat’s statistics on orders to leave, thus affecting comparability across Member States. Moreover, Member States do not always report data on orders to leave as per the Eurostat guidelines, e.g. when it comes to Dublin cases or double counting. This again affects comparability and makes it difficult to accurately interpret the indicator.
- The description of national practices behind issuing orders to leave and of the geographical specificities of the Member State is essential to better interpret

(71) Cour des comptes (2024), p. 57.

(72) Rechnungshof Österreich (2019), pp. 111-2.

the number of orders to leave. In France, for instance, the large number of orders to leave compared to other Member States can be attributed to the fact that authorities systematically issue orders to leave to irregularly staying TCNs, to the presence of oversea territories subject to significant irregular arrivals, and the police activities in areas of concentration of irregular TCNs, for instance in Calais.

- Return decisions or removals can be suspended for a number of reasons, linked to appeals or to legal and practical obstacles to return. These cases vary across Member States and data on suspended or valid orders to leave are not publicly and comprehensively available, neither in the EU nor at the national level. In Germany a complex system of toleration exists, and the available evidence points at the fact that the suspension of removal is a very significant phenomenon. The way statistics are collected (stock data), however, makes it difficult to compare it with the number of orders to leave annually issued.
- As the EU legislation does not regulate on non-returning persons, Member States implement a wide range of different approaches, from issuing temporary permits and to *de facto* suspending the return decision, to opening pathways to more stable residence. Some Member States foresee temporary authorisations of stay or toleration as long as the obstacles persist. The potential beneficiaries of these

temporary solutions, the conditions to access them, as well as the conditions under which the authorisation to stay can become independent from the persistence of the obstacles to return, vary.

- It is important to distinguish enforceable and non-enforceable return decisions, especially when assessing the effectiveness of return policies and to better understand what happens when to persons who do not return. The varying grounds on which statuses of tolerated stay are granted, and the possibility to convert these into other permits is not directly comparable across Member States. The lack of comparable data and information on temporary solutions when there are obstacles to return is a major limitation for the assessment of return effectiveness.
- The use of detention as a measure of last resort for enforcing return decisions is also subject to different national practices and limitations.
- Data on the use of pre-removal detention and alternatives to detention is scant. This hinders a thorough assessment of the effectiveness of these measures in return proceedings.
- Little information is available on the number of TCNs who absconded after a return decision.

3.2.1 Obligation to leave

At the national level, **the obligation to leave is disciplined through a range of acts (hence, generating several practices) that are much varied than those included in the Return Directive.**

- In **Spain**, two distinct acts establish the obligation to leave, on the one hand, and the initiation of the return proceedings, on the other.
 - The **obligation to leave** (*salida obligatoria*) is not directly linked to a return decision (unless aggravating circumstances other than irregular

stay are averted). It is rather a general obligation to leave the territory imposed on all third-country nationals who are identified as lacking a valid authorisation to stay⁽⁷³⁾. The obligation to leave is formally recorded: it can be included in the resolution rejecting the authorisation to stay, or noted in the TCN's passport or travel document, or in a separate document⁽⁷⁴⁾. However, an obligation to leave does not entail the initiation of return proceedings, and it differs from a return decision as defined in the Return Directive.

- **Return decisions** (*ordenes de expulsión*) are adopted in separate administrative procedures

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(73) This obligation must be complied with within a period of 15 days and is subject to a pecuniary fine. Article 24 Royal Decree 557/2011; Article 24(3), Royal Decree 1155/2024

(74) Article 24 Royal Decree 557/2011; Article 24(3), Royal Decree 1155/2024.

for cases who fail to comply with obligations to leave⁽⁷⁵⁾ and, generally, for third-country nationals who commit serious offenses⁽⁷⁶⁾ or who have been convicted for crimes carrying a prison sentence of more than one year⁽⁷⁷⁾. Return proceedings are initiated by national police authorities, and return decisions are issued by Delegated or Sub-Delegated Authorities in provincial administrations⁽⁷⁸⁾.

- In the **German** law, there is no unique procedure referring to ‘orders to leave’ or ‘return decisions’.

- Return decisions and obligations to return, as per the Return Directive, are translated as *Rückkehrentscheidung* and *Rückkehrverpflichtung*. These terms are not defined in the Residence Act which, in turn, refers to *Ausreisepflicht* as the **general obligation to leave** of TCNs without a right of residence⁽⁷⁹⁾. The country to which the person is required to return can include EU Member States or Schengen countries if the person is permitted to stay there, which may cover Dublin cases.

- **Removal warnings** (*Abschiebungsandrohung* and *Androhung der Abschiebung*)⁽⁸⁰⁾ refer to the intention to implement return procedures while allowing for a period for voluntary departure.

- In addition, a **removal order** ⁽⁸¹⁾ (*Abschiebungsanordnung*) can be issued by federal authorities (*Länder*) or the Ministry of the Interior in cases of security threats and is immediately enforceable⁽⁸²⁾.

- Finally, **expulsions** (*Asweidung*)⁽⁸³⁾ refer to the procedure to implement in specific case the stay of a foreigner endangers public safety and order, the free democratic basic order or other significant interests.

- Obligations to leave are issued by the asylum authority (the Federal Office for Migration and Refugees - BAMF) if they are a consequence of failed asylum proceedings, or by federal authorities for other third-country nationals.

- In **Italy**, **orders to leave** correspond to *decreti d'espulsione*⁽⁸⁴⁾, and are of two broad categories⁽⁸⁵⁾:

- **Administrative**, issued by the Prefecture to persons found to be irregularly staying or by the Ministry of the Interior, for reasons of public order or national security;

- Or **judicial**, issued as a consequence of criminal proceedings⁽⁸⁶⁾.

- Additionally, **first instance decisions** rejecting applications for international protection include a statement of the obligation to return and the prohibition of re-entry⁽⁸⁷⁾, which produces the effects of an obligation to leave.

- In **Austria** the authorities are generally required to issue return decisions to all third-country nationals not residing legally in Austria.

- Return decisions (*Rückkehrentscheidungen*)⁽⁸⁸⁾ are issued in particular on the basis of three

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(75) Article 24 (2), Royal Decree 557/2011; Article 24 (3), Real Decreto 1155/2024.

(76) According to Articles 57(1) and 53(1) of Organic Law 4/2000, serious offenses leading to return decisions include illegal stay; falsifying or concealing information related to nationality, marital status, or domicile; failure to comply with measures imposed on grounds of public security –e.g., such as periodic reporting to authorities; or participation in activities that threaten public order and security.

(77) Article 57(2), Organic Law 4/2000.

(78) Policia Nacional (n.d).

(79) Section 50, Residence Act (Aufenthaltsgesetz).

(80) Section 59, Residence Act (Aufenthaltsgesetz) and Section 34a, Asylum Act.

(81) This term is used in the English translation of the Residence Act.

(82) Section 58a, Residence Act (Aufenthaltsgesetz).

(83) Section 53, Residence Act (Aufenthaltsgesetz). It is specified that the interest of the country and the individual interest in remaining in the territory should be carefully assessed and weighted.

(84) Article 13, Legislative Decree 25 July 1998, n. 286 (Consolidated Act on Immigration).

(85) EMN Italy (2023).

(86) Removal can be ordered as a security measure, as an alternative to detention for persons who have a definitive sentence or for persons charged for crimes which carry less than 2-year prison terms, and as an alternative to the pecuniary fine for illegal entry and stay, according to Article 16 of the Consolidated Act on Immigration.

(87) Article 32(4), Legislative Decree 28 January 2008, n. 25 on the “Implementation of Directive 2005/85/EC laying down minimum standards for the procedures applied in the Member States for the purpose of recognising and withdrawing refugee status”.

(88) Article 52, Aliens Police Act 2005.

circumstances: a) a negative decision on an application for international protection; b) a determination of irregular stay; c) withdrawal of an international protection status.

- In all cases, the admissibility of a return decision is assessed based on Art. 2, 3 and 8 of the ECHR. If the review of possible refoulement violations is positive, the person will receive a residence permit for exceptional circumstances ex officio⁽⁸⁹⁾. The competent authority for issuing a return decision, the refoulement review and the granting of a residence permit for exceptional circumstances is the Federal Office for Immigration and Asylum (BFA).
- Other procedures include removal orders (*Anordnung zur Außerlandesbringung*)⁽⁹⁰⁾ covering Dublin cases or TCNs who already benefit from protection in another Member State), and expulsions (*Ausweisung*) for reasons of public policy or security⁽⁹¹⁾.
- In **France**, orders to leave correspond to *Obligation de Quitter le Territoire Français* (OQTF)⁽⁹²⁾. They are issued to⁽⁹³⁾: i) TCNs without a valid permit of stay or whose permit or visa has expired; ii) TCNs whose permit's renewal has been rejected or whose permit has been withdrawn; iii) asylum applicants, whose applications have been rejected at final instance; iv) TCNs who have not been residing regularly for more than three months and represent a threat for public order or contravene labour law.

The OQTF is issued by the prefects. Ministerial circulars⁽⁹⁴⁾ have clarified that the prefects should issue orders to leave *systematically*, to any TCN in the situations described above (see also Box 14). Following legislative amendments introduced in 2024 (Law 2024-42), OQTF can be executed for a period of three years from their date of issue⁽⁹⁵⁾.

Other national measures can be applied to TCNs in an irregular situation, notably: i) expulsions in case of threat to fundamental societal interests, generally accompanied by entry bans, ii) Schengen readmissions, iii) bans from the French territory issued by the judiciary in case of criminal law⁽⁹⁶⁾.

Annex 3 summarises the various definitions of obligations to leave in national legislation.

These different analytical categories at the national level make it difficult to pin down which cases are covered by Eurostat's statistics on orders to leave (migr_eiord – See Box 7).

- In the **Spanish** case, for statistical purposes, only return decisions (*ordenes de expulsión*) are communicated as 'orders to leave' in the statistics gathered by Eurostat.
- In the **German** case the fact that the terms linked to the obligation to leave do not univocally map on the terminology of the Return Directive makes it difficult to identify which categories are covered by Eurostat statistics of persons subject to an obligation to leave⁽⁹⁷⁾. National studies often refer to orders to leave as removal warnings (EMN 2017), thus potentially excluding the persons who are subject to an obligation to leave that does not grant a period of voluntary departure.

In addition, while Eurostat guidelines establish that third-country nationals subject to a Dublin procedure should not be recorded under the statistics on persons subject to an obligation to leave, according to the national metadata reports **in France, Germany, Italy and Spain it cannot be ensured that Dublin cases are excluded** from these statistics.

Moreover, while Eurostat guidelines dictate that persons should be counted only once, **France, Italy and Spain also state that double counting is not excluded**,

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(89) In accordance with paragraph 55 und 57 of the Federal Act concerning the Granting of Asylum (Asylum Act – AsylG).

(90) Article 61, Aliens Police Act.

(91) Article 66, Aliens Police Act.

(92) The CESEDA is the main legal instrument.

(93) Article L611-1 of the CESEDA.

(94) e.g. circulaire dated 20 November 2017.

(95) Article 72 of Law 2024-42 of 26 January 2024, which modified Article L731-1 of the CESEDA.

(96) Cour des comptes (2024), p.52.

(97) As per Eurostat Guidelines, "such obligation to leave is called a 'return decision' in EU law".

which means several return decisions issued to the same person may be included. While both Germany and Italy issue return decisions together with negative decisions on asylum applications, only the latter reports to include rejected asylum applications in persons

ordered to leave statistics. The German metadata on persons ordered to leave states that asylum and return statistics are not linked and tap into two different sources⁽⁹⁸⁾.

Box 14. Magnitude of orders to leave in France.

France is the country that since 2017 has been consistently issuing the highest number of orders to leave in the EU, reaching 37% of the EU total in 2021 (Figure 9). The second top EU countries for orders to leave represented a much lower share over time, between 16% and 9% of the EU total.

The most important nationalities receiving orders to leave in France in the period 2021-2023 are Algerians (18% of total), Moroccans and Tunisians (each 8%), followed by Albanians, Bangladeshis and Georgians (each 4%). In this period, France was also the Member State that issued the relative majority of orders to leave to its top three nationalities (50% of total EU orders to leave issued to Algerians, Moroccans and Tunisians).

According to the French Court of Auditors, **the gap between France and the other Member States is due the fact that France systematically issues OTL to all TCN in an irregular situation**, following the ministerial circular dated 20 November 2017 and the Return Directive.

National data shed light on the pathways leading to irregularity and order to leave. According to data included in a report by the French Court of auditors, of the 447,257 OQTF issued in the period 2019-2022, 22% resulted from a rejected residence permit, 28% from a rejected asylum application, 39% from police arrests of irregularly staying TCNs, and another 5% from TCNs who committed a disturbance of public order.

Overstay and persons found to be irregularly present on the territory represent a significant share of persons receiving an order to leave, while asylum is relatively less significant (in line with what was discussed in Section 3.1.2.3). France is the only country where orders to leave exceed the number of persons found to be irregularly present, signalling that most TCNs identified as irregularly staying eventually receive an order to leave. This is remarkable compared with other Member States, where the number of persons found to be irregularly present by far outnumbers the other indicators (Figure 7).

National data on the number of TCNs found in an irregular situation (étrangers en situation irrégulière procédurés) point at three regions where most procedures on TCNs found to be irregularly present were initiated: Nord-Pas-de-Calais-Picardie (with more than 15,000 TCNs identified as irregularly present in 2022), Provence-Alpes-Cote d’Azur, and Languedoc-Rousillon-Midi-Pyrénées (each with between 10,000 and 15,000 TCNs identified as irregularly present in 2022)⁽⁹⁹⁾.

In addition, data for the same period show that half of OQTF were taken by only 10 prefectures, demonstrating differentiated migratory pressure⁽¹⁰⁰⁾.

.....

(98) Cour des comptes (2024), p. 57, based on data retrieved from the AGDREF information system. AGDREF (application of management of the files of the foreign nationals in France) is an information system managed by the Directorate General for Foreigners of the Ministry of the Interior which provides information data on the administrative situation of foreigners in France (residence permits, removal measures). It contains data on different categories of foreign residents, including photographs and fingerprints.

(99) Cour des comptes (2024), p.29.

(100) These are: Paris, Seine-Saint-Denis, Mayotte, Hauts-de-Seine, Nord, Val d’Oise, Bouches-du-Rhône, Pas-de-Calais, Guyane, Val-de-Marne.

Until 2024, another important factor to consider when comparing France to other Member States was the **rapid obsolescence of the orders to leave**, that needed to be re-examined if not enforced within one year⁽¹⁰¹⁾. The Court of Auditors reports that during the period 2019-2022 more than 43,000 TCNs (10% of the total orders to leave)⁽¹⁰²⁾ received multiple OTLs. In 2024, this period was extended to three years⁽¹⁰³⁾.

Finally, the role of **overseas territory** should also be considered. Mayotte is the top third prefecture issuing orders to leave, and Guyane the top eight. In Mayotte in particular, the prefecture estimates that between 24,000 and 28,000 persons arrive irregularly each year by boat.

FIGURE 9. Orders to leave issued by France since 2014, in absolute numbers and as a share of EU total.

Source: Eurostat, migr_eiord.

3.2.2 Postponement of the obligation to leave or of removal

The return decision may be postponed if the third-country national appeals the return decision, or the asylum decision if she or he previously applied for asylum. The effect of the appeals differs across Member States:

- In **Austria**, return decisions are generally issued together with negative decisions on international protection applications. First appeals against both types of decisions (asylum and return decisions) carry an automatic suspensive effect. Further appeals lack automatic suspension but this can be requested⁽¹⁰⁴⁾. A large second instance caseload has been identified as a relevant factor in explaining the gap between return decisions and implemented returns in Austria⁽¹⁰⁵⁾.

(101) Cour des comptes (2024), p.101.

(102) This is coherent with the information reported in Eurostat French metadata, that estimate a double counting of 5%. See: Eurostat, National reference metadata. France. Enforcement of Immigration Legislation (migr_eil), https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cache/metadata/EN/migr_eil_esqrs_fr.htm (Accessed: July 2024). While the Eurostat indicator is 'third-country nationals ordered to leave', the national definition refers to the number of administrative measures or procedures for third-country nationals ordered to leave, as reported in the French Eurostat's metadata.

(103) Article 72 of Law n. 2024-42 of 26 January 2024, which introduced amendments to Article L731-1 of the CESEDA.

(104) Lukits, R (2016); EMN (2017); ECRE (2023).

(105) The Court of Audit Reported there were over 30,000 pending cases at the end of 2018. Rechnungshof (2019).

FIGURE 10. Possible outcomes of suspended of return decisions due to obstacles to return.

- In **France**, return decisions are issued separately from negative asylum decisions, and can be appealed before administrative tribunals. Appeals do not carry an automatic suspensive effect, but this can be requested. A further recourse before the Administrative Court of Appeal is also possible⁽¹⁰⁶⁾.
- In **Spain**, the suspensive effect of appealing against a return decision is not automatic, but it is often granted during the appeal stage or when the third-country national applies for a residence permit. Asylum decisions are issued separately from return decisions, which means that appeals against negative asylum decisions do not have an effect on return decisions.
- In **Italy**⁽¹⁰⁷⁾ and **Germany**, appeals against first instance asylum decisions generally⁽¹⁰⁸⁾ suspend the obligation to return. Suspensory effects linked to appeal processes are limited in time, and will only delay the enforceability of return until the decision

is confirmed at a higher instance. In some cases, the appeal can take several months or years⁽¹⁰⁹⁾. In **Germany**, appeals against return decisions not issued in the context of asylum procedures do not have an automatic suspensive effect, but this can be requested by the claimants⁽¹¹⁰⁾. This is also the case in **Italy** for appeals against administrative return decisions, as these are immediately enforceable, but their suspension can be granted by the Court⁽¹¹¹⁾. Judicial return decisions in Italy, on the contrary, are not enforceable until appeals have been exhausted⁽¹¹²⁾.

Return will also be postponed in cases where obstacles to return are linked to non-refoulement, and may be postponed due to practical obstacles for the person to leave a Member State’s territory. All the case studies have mechanisms in place to address these situations. These mechanisms either give immediate access to a permit (*de facto* regularising the stay of the person – see Section 3.3.2), or provide for

(106) EUAA (2024).
 (107) There are two possible appeal instances in Italy. First-instance decisions issued by the Territorial Commissions can be appealed before the Civil Courts (Articles 35 (1) and 35-bis(1), Legislative Decree 25/2008). An onward appeal against decisions of the Civil Courts is possible before the Court of Cassation (Article 35-bis(1), Legislative Decree 25/2008).
 (108) In Germany, suspensive effect applies only to applications channelled through the regular procedure, and excludes those rejected as manifestly unfounded.
 (109) The average length of an asylum procedure in Germany was 6.6 months in 2021, with a slight increase to 7.6 months in the first half of 2022 (Deutscher Bundestag, 2023b). The time until a decision is reached differs by nationality (with for instance 14.9 months for Nigerian citizens and 1.3 months for Moldovan citizens, Bundestag, 2022: 11). However, it usually took longer until a judicially non-appealable decision was reached. Judicial appeals have gradually increased the overall length of the procedures from 8.7 months in 2016 to 17.6 months in 2018 to 24 months in 2021. A major reason for the delays is a large number of decisions issued by the BAMF have been “flawed or declared unlawful”. 36 per cent of the original material decisions reviewed by the courts were overturned in 2021 (Deutscher Bundestag, 2023b: 1)
 (110) European Migration Network (2017).
 (111) Constitutional Court, Judgement 161/2000.
 (112) Article 16 (7), Consolidated Act on Immigration.

temporary solutions. These latter consist in toleration or in a temporary residence permit conditional to the duration of the obstacles to return. In some cases, after a tolerated period, or on a temporary permit, and if certain conditions are met, it is possible to transition to more durable statuses which do not depend on the continuity of the obstacles to return, and which are described in Section 3.3.2.1.

Germany and Austria foresee a formal **toleration status** in their legislation. In both cases, the obligation to return remains in place, but its enforcement is temporarily suspended.

- **Austria's** tolerated stay status (*Duldung*) can be granted if the return decision cannot be enforced due to legal or practical obstacles. Examples of legal obstacles include non-refoulement grounds, while practical obstacles may arise in cases where, for instance, removal cannot be enforced due to lack of cooperation from the country of origin or when a readmission agreement is not in place. Tolerated stay is not granted in cases where the individuals concerned

refuse to cooperate with the authorities in the return process, for example for identity determination. Persons granted tolerated stay receive an ID card for tolerated stay, which is valid for one year and can be extended⁽¹¹³⁾.

- **Germany** has a more complex system with various types of tolerated statuses (*Duldung*) (Box 15). A general *Duldung* is normally granted for 3 to 6 months, and is renewable as long as the obstacles to return persist. The rights provided by the general *Duldung* differ depending on whether the identity of the person is verified and whether he or she cooperated with the authorities to this end (see *Duldung* light in Box 15). There are two more specific types of *Duldung*: the *Duldung* for training and for employment. Available to those who spent some months on the general *Duldung*, their aim is to avoid the indefinite renewals of *Duldung* (phenomenon called 'chain toleration')⁽¹¹⁴⁾, and provide for more sustainable pathways out of toleration to persons integrating in the German society and with a verified identity⁽¹¹⁵⁾ (Box 15).

Box 15. *Duldung* in the German legislation.

According to the German Residence Act (Section 60), in general the *Duldung* applies in the following circumstances:

- The supreme land authorities may suspend the deportation to specific states for reasons related to international law, humanitarian grounds, or for political interests (60a (1));
- The deportation is to be suspended if:
 - it is impossible by law or practice and no residence permit is granted (60a (1));
 - the person is involved in criminal proceedings that require his or her presence (60a (2));
 - there are urgent humanitarian or personal grounds or substantial public interest (60a (2));
 - the procedure for the acknowledgement of the paternity is suspended (60a (1));
 - the deportation or removal has failed (60a (2a));

(113) Stiller, M. and L. Humer (2020), p. 13. The toleration ID card will be withdrawn if its period of validity has expired; the requirements for toleration are not or are no longer met; the photograph on the card no longer clearly identifies the holder; or other official entries on the card have become illegible Aliens Police Act.

(114) Haberstroh et al., (2022).

(115) Or who cooperated with the authorities in the verification process.

- the person is a parent or has the custody of a minor with a residence permit (60a (2b));
- the person has an illness that might interfere with deportation (60a (2c and 2d));

A person with tolerated status may take up **work**, generally after an initial period of three months.

A more specific form of *Duldung* was introduced in 2016, the ‘**Duldung light**’, for persons without a verified identity who did not support the authorities in the identification process. It does not allow to work and restricts freedom of movement within Germany (Residence Act, Section 60b).

The *Duldung* for training or for employment purposes, introduced in 2020, on the contrary, provides more rights to the person, and after their time of validity they both offer the option of regularisation:

- **Duldung for training purposes** (*AusbildungsDuldung*): for persons starting a vocational training in a regulated occupation, or starting a training as assistant or helper in a regulated profession that may lead to vocational training in an occupation where shortages exist (Residence Act, Section 60c). To access, the TCN must have a verified identity and be a rejected asylum applicant, or tolerated for the past 3 months. The three-year period of professional education and training is followed by the possibility of pursuing an activity for a further two years (Stache, 2024).
- **Duldung for employment purposes** (*BeschäftigungsDuldung*): for persons (and by extension, their spouses and unmarried children) who entered Germany before 2018, whose identity has been verified (or the person has cooperated in the process, even if unsuccessful), who had a *Duldung* for the past 12 months, and who were in employment for the past 18 months (Residence Act, Section 60d). In addition, the employment should ensure the subsistence of the person, who has to show at least elementary command of the German language, and no conviction or link to terrorist organization. The toleration lasts 30 months.

In some cases, **persons for whom there are obstacles to return have access to a temporary permit, while the return decision is still valid**⁽¹¹⁸⁾. In Austria and Germany, the access to these permits often occurs after a period of toleration.

- In **Austria**, the **residence permit for special protection** (*Aufenthaltsberechtigung besonderer Schutz*)⁽¹¹⁹⁾ is available to: i) persons who have been tolerated for 12 months and for whom the obstacles to return persist (upon application or granted ex officio)⁽¹²⁰⁾; ii) to witnesses or victims of trafficking or of violence. Another

option is the **residence permit on the grounds of Article 8 of the ECHR** (*Aufenthaltstitel aus Gründen des Art. 8 EMRK*)⁽¹²¹⁾ that covers cases related to the maintenance of private and family life. These two permits last 12 months and only the residence permit for special protection is renewable, provided requirements are still met. After 12 months, TCNs become eligible for a **residence permit**⁽¹²²⁾ that is not linked to the persistence of any obstacles to return.

- In **Germany**, if toleration lasts more than 6 months, the Land authority may issue a **temporary residence**

.....

(116) If he or she is not responsible for the obstacles to return, he or she did not enter Germany to claim asylum benefits, and he or she is not a rejected asylum applicant from a safe country (Hoffmeyer-Zlotnik, P. (2017).
 (117) Originally this possibility was due to expire on 31 December 2023, but the expiration has been.
 (118) Depending on the permits, the TCN would have more rights than on toleration, for instance on labour market access.
 (119) Article 57, paragraph 1, subparagraph 1 of the Asylum Act. EMN (2021).
 (120) This does not apply to TCN whose international protection status (refugee or subsidiary protection status) has been withdrawn. Hinterberger, K.F (2023).
 (121) Article 55, Asylum Act.
 (122) Red-White-Red plus card or settlement permits as per Articles 41 and 43 of the Settlement and Residence Act. EMN (2021), Responses to long-term irregularly staying migrants: Practices and challenges in EU Member States and Norway.

permit⁽¹²³⁾. Temporary residence permits are not renewable if the obstacles to departure cease to apply⁽¹²⁴⁾.

- **Italy’s “special protection”** (*protezione speciale*) permit is specifically designed for persons who cannot be returned due to non-refoulement concerns. Currently, it is granted only to rejected international protection applicants and it is issued for a 2-year period, with the possibility of renewal. The renewal is conditional on the evaluation of the asylum committee as to the validity of the conditions that led to the issuance of the permit in the first place. Following legislative

changes introduced in in 2023⁽¹²⁵⁾, this permit cannot be converted in a work permit, which would make the regular status of the person independent from the persistence of the obstacles to return (Box 16). Persons issued special protection permits are not subjects of return decisions.

Spain and **France** do not have a tolerated stay status or a legal distinction between different categories of irregular TCNs, but instead relies on issuing residence permits to prevent long-term irregularity (see Section 3.3.2.1).

Box 16. Special protection permits in Italy.

The residence permit for special protection (*permesso di soggiorno per protezione speciale*) was introduced in 2018 through Legislative Decree 113/2018, also known as the “Salvini Decree,” which was converted into Law 132/2018. This legislation replaced the previous humanitarian residence permit with a new special protection permit, issued to third-country nationals who do not qualify for international protection but cannot be returned to their countries of origin due to the principle of non-refoulement. The asylum authorities make decisions on granting special protection, while the police (Questura) issue the permits.

In 2020, a new law expanded the criteria for issuing the permit to include situations where return would violate the right to private and family life, taking into account the applicant’s family ties and social integration in Italy. Additionally, it allowed individuals who had not applied for asylum but were staying in Italy irregularly to apply for the permit directly with the police.

However, a 2023 law reversed these changes, limiting the cases where expulsion can be prohibited and consequently restricting the issuance of residence permits for special protection.

These legislative changes may have impacted the use of this permit as a pathway out of irregularity and the size of the population considered to be irregularly staying in Italy. Until 2020, the number of persons ordered to leave coincided with those found to be illegally present. However, between 2020 and 2021, the number of persons found to be illegally present increased by 360%, from 22,000 to 92,000.

Previous analyses have linked this increase to the implementation of the “Salvini Decree”. According to Eurostat’s metadata report for Italy, rejected asylum applications are included among persons found to be illegally present. Eurostat’s guidelines indicate to categorise rejected asylum applicants as “overstay” in the reason field. However, as seen in Section 3.1.1, in Italy, nearly all cases of TCNs found to be illegally present during 2021–2023 were attributed to irregular entries. It remains thus unclear whether the recent increase effectively originates from the asylum system.

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(123) Section 60a (1), Residence Act refers to Article 23(1) on granting a residence permit by the supreme Land authorities. Duldung is not a necessary requirements for the permits covered by Article 23(1) and can be granted to persons who did not receive a Duldung under the discretion of the Land authority.

(124) Section 26(2), Residence Act.

(125) Legislative Decree 10 March 2023, n.20 on “Urgent provisions regarding the legal entry of foreign workers and the prevention and contrast of irregular migration” (also known as “Cutro Decree”), and converted into Law 5 May 2023, n. 5.

FIGURE 11. Toleration cards issued in Austria, 2011-2022.

Source: Parliamentary enquiries.

Note: Data for 2021 are missing and for 2020 incomplete.

The different types of residence permits issued as a consequence of obstacles to return are summarised in Annex 2.

At the EU level, statistics on the suspended orders to leave or suspended enforcement are not available⁽¹²⁶⁾. At national level, data availability varies. Austria and Germany, for example, collect data on toleration in their national databases. These are **not generally available to the public in their entirety**, but can be retrieved in parliamentary enquiries or via the national statistical offices in aggregated manner (Box 17).

- In **Austria**, data available through parliamentary enquiries⁽¹²⁷⁾ covers the 2011-2022 period⁽¹²⁸⁾, and suggests that toleration has been used very restrictively, with a maximum of 355 cards issued in 2013 (Figure 11). The low number of tolerated cards compared to the orders to leave is often explained as consequence of the authorities' assessment on the third-country national cooperation – which is a

pre-condition to be granted a tolerated status⁽¹²⁹⁾.

- In **Germany**, one of the latest parliamentary enquiries⁽¹³⁰⁾ provides a wealth of information on the number of persons with a *Duldung* and the reasons. Contrary to the Austrian experience, **this instrument is widely used in Germany**. As of 30 June 2023, there were 224,768 persons with a tolerated status in AZR, out of a total of 279,098 persons with an obligation to leave. This means that the vast majority of persons with an obligation to leave in Germany (81%) had a *Duldung*. The most common *Duldung* is the simple *Duldung*, based on Section 60a(2) of the Residence Act (Table 2). One third of persons with *Duldung* had been staying in the country for 3 years or less (32%), while more than half (59%) for 6 years or more. These numbers cannot be compared with orders to leave issued in a reference period (flow indicator) as they describe pending cases at a given point in time (stock indicator).

(126) Italy reports special protection permits under "Humanitarian protection" decisions in Eurostat's first instance decisions dataset. See Fondazione ISMU (2023).

(127) See: Bundesministerium für Inneres, reply to parliamentary enquiries 196/J ;8373/J; 3663/J; and 14357/J

(128) Data for 2021 is not available

(129) EMN (2021).

(130) Deutscher Bundestag (2023c).

TABLE 2. Types of *Duldung* issued in Germany as of 30 June 2023.

Residence Act reference	Value	% of total
60a - Old	359	0%
60a(1) - International law, humanitarian ground, political interest	3,391	2%
60a(2) - Impossible in fact or by law	190,710	85%
60b - Duldung light	20,909	9%
60c - Training Duldung	5,131	2%
60d - Employment Duldung	3,382	2%
60a(2a) - Deportation failed	-	0%
60a(2b) - Parent of minor	886	0%

Note: Parliamentary enquiry (Deutscher Bundestag (2023c)) based on AZR data.

Box 17. German national data on Duldung and orders to leave.

The German statistical office, DESTATIS, reports data on the number of registered people holding a general *Duldung*, latently required to leave⁽¹³¹⁾ or forcibly required to leave⁽¹³²⁾.

Since 2007, the number of persons with tolerated status has always been much larger than the number of persons required to leave (latently or enforceable). Since 2015 the gap between these numbers started to increase, just to slightly reduce in 2023.

Year on year, the stock of tolerated persons has steadily increased up to 2023. The stock of persons forcibly required to leave increased in 2015, to start decreasing again in 2019. The stock of persons latently required to leave started to increase in 2016 to stabilise at values between 13,000 and 18,000 afterwards.

FIGURE 12. DESTATIS, Code: 12531-0007. Blue: Duldung (60(a) of the Residence Act, required to leave, deportation temporarily suspended), Red: persons forcibly required to leave (58(2) of the Residence Act); Green: latently required to leave (50(1) of the Residence Act).

(131) DESTATIS does not provide specific definitions of latently and forcibly required to leave, but refer to the specific articles of the reference legislation, respectively: Section 50(1), Section 58(2) of the Residence Act.
 (132) The dataset is called 'people seeking protection', so it refers to people who at some point applied for asylum. Other studies report data from AZR. Rietig, V. and Günnewig, M.L. (2020)) reports the number of persons with an obligation to leave with and without a tolerated status. Compared to DESATIS, the numbers are higher, probably due to the fact that DESTATIS reports statistics only on people seeking protection.

3.2.3 Evasion of the enforcement of the obligation to leave

In the process of return, some third-country nationals **abscond**, evading enforcement of the obligation to leave. Detention and alternatives to detention (e.g. reporting obligations, residence restrictions, and the handing over of documents) are often used to minimise the risk of absconding.

- **Pre-removal detention** is considered a measure of last resort in **Germany**. However, in recent years laws to strengthen return policies have been introduced, including the expansion of “detention pending departure” (*Ausreisegewahrsam*) in the proximity of airports. Most recently, the Act to Improve the Return of Foreigners (2024) has **extended detention pending departure from 10 to 28 days** to prevent absconding.
- In **Spain**, pre-removal detention is limited to cases when there is a **reasonable prospect of removal**, and mostly applied against those involved in criminal proceedings. It last up to 60 days.
- In **Italy**⁽¹³³⁾ and **France**,⁽¹³⁴⁾ **pre-removal detention is subject to judicial validation** and can last respectively 90 days or 18 months.

Data on pre-removal detention is generally scarce, but is sometimes made available through National Human Rights Institutions (Italy and Spain)⁽¹³⁵⁾ or civil society organisations (Italy,⁽¹³⁶⁾ France⁽¹³⁷⁾ and Spain⁽¹³⁸⁾). However, the lack of comprehensive and reliable data on detention places hinders an assessment of the effectiveness of pre-removal detention in the enforcement of return decisions. These types of assessments have not been systematically conducted across Member

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(133) Article 14, Consolidated Act on Immigration.
 (134) As per Law n. 2011-672 of 16 June 2011 on immigration, integration and nationality and its implementing Decree (Decree n. 2011-820 of 8 July 2011).
 (135) The Italian National Ombudsperson for the Rights of Detained Persons (Garante nazionale dei diritti delle persone private della libertà personale - GNPL) publishes regular reports on the situation in pre-removal centres (Centri di Permanenza per il Rimpatrio - CPR). Similarly The Spanish Ombudsperson (Defensor del Pueblo) publishes annual reports in the context of the national mechanism for the prevention of torture (Mecanismo Nacional de Prevencion) which includes data on pre-removal detention centres (Centros de Internamiento de Extranjeros - CIE).
 (136) As part of the “Trattenuti” Project, ActionAid and the University of Bari have made available data on the management of pre-removal centres, including on inflows and outflows of detainees. More information is available on the Project’s website: <https://trattenuti.actionaid.it/>
 (137) La Cimade (2023).
 (138) Servicio Jesuita de Migrantes (2022).
 (139) Available studies have found no correlation between detention and increased returns in Germany (Rietig, V. and Günnewig, M.L. (2020); Mediendienst Integration (2023)).
 (140) In Italy, data is often retrievable in reports by civil society organisations. According to the European Council for Refugees and Exiles’ (ECRE) 2023 Report, 968 alternative measures were granted in 2021, and 343 had been granted by 31 May 2022 to persons granted a period for voluntary. In Germany, it has been reported that alter alternatives to detention are used rather rarely (see e.g. Ibid: 21, Mielke et al., 2024: 39 and 44; Hoffmeyer-Zlotnik/Stiller, 2023c).

States. Even when detention data is available, it is challenging to assess its impact due to the absence of a clear distinction between enforceable and non-enforceable obligations to leave. Moreover, focusing the analysis only on people in detention and their chance to return may disregard some other factors that are relevant to explain return patterns (thus being subject to a selection bias).⁽¹³⁹⁾

Similarly, **data on the use of alternatives to detention is scant**.⁽¹⁴⁰⁾

The Member States analysed do not **record the number of absconded persons with an order to leave**.

In **Germany**, the Central Register of Foreigners foresees the option to register that a person has moved to an unknown location (*Fortzug nach Unbekannt*), if a person cannot be traced. This can be due to a spontaneous or voluntary return, but also because a person absconded. At the moment, however, no information is publicly available on the number of persons with a return decision who moved to an unknown location.

3.3 Exiting irregularity

There are two main pathways out of irregularity: return and authorised stay or residence. While it emerges from the Return Directive that return should be the “default” measure when irregularly staying third-country nationals are identified, the Directive also entails a degree of **flexibility to implement other pathways to deal with irregularity** (Article 6 - see Box 8). The guiding questions, whose answers are summarised in the ‘Key takeaways’ Section, are:

- Are there specific national practices aimed at boosting voluntary returns? Which data are available to describe (assisted or unassisted) voluntary as well as forced returns?
- To what extent do Member States grant access to a residence permit to persons with an obligation to leave? Which data are available to describe this phenomenon?

Key takeaways exiting irregularity

- In line with the Directive’s indications, Member States have in place practices aimed at boosting voluntary returns, including different periods for voluntary departure and access to return counselling at various stages of the return process.
- Data on these practices are limited, limiting the assessment of their effectiveness.
- Forced return has been predominant in France, Italy and Spain. In Germany, data on voluntary returns are scattered across different sources and not comprehensively available.
- At the national level, there are different analytical categories to classify returns and this in some cases poses difficulties in comparability with Eurostat (e.g. for Spain).
- Authorities struggle to record unassisted voluntary returns and only France and Austria provide such statistics; this may lead to an underestimation of the actual returns.
- While it emerges from the Return Directive that return should be the “default” measure, Member States have developed different approaches in the management of irregular migration, including the issuing of residence permits or authorisations to stay.
- In the absence of an EU framework on regularisation, a variety of procedures are implemented at the national level, making it challenging to compare data across Member States.
- Requirements for accessing residence permits or authorisations vary across Member States, but are generally linked to integration, employment, or humanitarian grounds.
- The availability of data on residence permits or authorisations varies across Member States. Where data is publicly available, it reveals diverse patterns, with Spain and France exhibiting a significant use of these instruments, and Austria a more limited one.
- The lack of comparable EU data on accesses to residence permits after being in an irregular status or receiving an order to leave represent a significant evidence gap when analysing the status of non-returned persons, and consequently the effectiveness of return.

3.3.1 Return

3.3.1.1 Practices on voluntary return

While the 2021 EU Strategy on Voluntary Return and Coordination presented by the European Commission aimed to reduce the fragmentation of approaches at national level, **Member States currently put in place different practices to encourage voluntary returns.** These include the time allowed for voluntary

departure, return counselling, and the rules on the accessibility of assistance during the return procedure, and the type of assistance received.

The duration of the period for voluntary departure mandated by the Directive varies across countries.

- In **Germany**, the period for voluntary departure is generally set at **30 days**, unless it concerns applicants for asylum rejected as manifestly unfounded, in which case it is reduced to one week⁽¹⁴¹⁾.

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(141) ECRE (2025).

- In **Austria**, this period is generally set at **14 days** from the moment the return decision becomes enforceable. However, in case of special circumstances, this deadline can be fixed once for a longer period⁽¹⁴²⁾.
- In **Spain** the obligation to leave (*salida obligatoria*) allows for a period of voluntary departure of 15 days. In addition, following the issuance of a return decision (*orden de expulsión*) there is a **second period for voluntary departure of 7 to 30 days**⁽¹⁴³⁾.
- In **Italy**, the period for voluntary departure **must be requested to the Prefect**. This option is not available to those who have received return decisions based on grounds of national security, public order, or where there is a risk of absconding. Additionally, asylum or residence permit applicants whose claims have been deemed manifestly unfounded or fraudulent are also excluded⁽¹⁴⁴⁾.

Data on the number of persons granted a period of voluntary departure, or who are in such condition, are not publicly available in the Member States analysed.

Return counselling is available in all Member States⁽¹⁴⁵⁾, although different approaches exist across and within Member States in terms of the actors involved, the obligation to receive counselling, and the way counselling is provided. In Austria, return counselling with the Federal Agency for Reception and Support Services (BBU), which includes information on accessing reintegration assistance after return, is mandatory. In the other Member States, return counselling does not seem to be mandatory. In Austria, Italy, France and Germany, **state and non-state actors** are involved in counselling; while in Spain only NGOs provide this service⁽¹⁴⁶⁾. In Germany, there is a network of about 600 foreign authorities and 1,500 counselling centres of welfare organisations and non-governmental organisations⁽¹⁴⁷⁾ providing different forms of return counselling and assistance.

In Austria, Germany and Italy, return counselling is available even before the negative asylum decision or the order to leave, while in Spain only after the return decision⁽¹⁴⁸⁾. In the first group of countries, **the potential beneficiaries of return counselling is thus larger than those TCNs who are required to leave**⁽¹⁴⁹⁾.

In general, the possibility to voluntary return temporarily precedes forced return. However, in Austria for instance, persons undergoing forced return procedures can opt to **access voluntary return** at any point of the process.

No information is publicly available on the number of beneficiaries of return counselling, their use of assisted voluntary return and reintegration programmes, and whether they received a return decision.

3.3.1.2 Statistics on return by type

Eurostat statistics provide a disaggregation of persons returned after an order to leave by type of return (Box 9). Austria, France, Italy, Spain report the data by (assisted or unassisted) voluntary returns and assisted forced returns. Germany, on the contrary, reports values only for forced returns, which therefore make up the total number of returns⁽¹⁵⁰⁾. **The majority of returns following an order to leave appears to be forced**, with percentages ranging from 100% in the case of Germany, 95% in Italy, 70% in Spain, and 56% in France (Figure 13). The only exception is Austria, that reports only 19% forced returns in the period 2021-2023.

Tracking unassisted returns is challenging as the third-country nationals may leave without notifying the authorities. **Austria** and **France** are the only countries that distinguish between assisted and unassisted voluntary returns, but there is limited information on the accuracy of this data and on the methodologies used to capture the phenomenon. In Austria, TCNs departing

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(142) Article 55, paragraphs 2 and 3, Aliens Police Act.

(143) Article 63bis, Organic Law 4/2000.

(144) Article 13, Consolidated Act on Immigration.

(145) EMN (2019), EMN inform on return counselling. Policies and practices on return counselling for migrants in EU member states and Norway. https://www.emn.at/wp-content/uploads/2019/08/emn_inform-2019-return-counselling.pdf

(146) EMN (2019).

(147) Grote, J. (2015).

(148) EMN (2019).

(149) EMN (2019).

(150) Voluntary returns are 0, according to Eurostat's eitrn_vol.

FIGURE 13. Total returns and returns by type in the period 2021-23.

Source: Eurostat, [migr_eirtn] and [migr_eirtn1]. When not visible, total return equals total return by type.

voluntarily and with assistance are accompanied by BBU staff to their point of departure. TCNs departing without assistance are asked to provide confirmation of leaving the country to border authorities or to Austrian representations in the country of destination, allowing to monitor unassisted returns to some extent. In both cases, during the period 2021-2023, the share between the assisted and unassisted voluntary return is approximately even (Austria), or slightly in favour of assisted voluntary return (France).

The **sum of returns by type and the total number of returns across different Eurostat datasets⁽¹⁵¹⁾ is generally consistent**, even if the numbers do not perfectly match. The only exception is Spain, where the number of returns disaggregated by type is larger by 29% than the total number of returns, in the period 2021-2023. No information is available on the reasons behind the mismatch.

In some cases, **national data** provide additional information or different categorisations than the ones from Eurostat.

- In **France** there is a first distinction between returns concerning persons ordered to leave (*éloignements*) and those concerning persons who were not issued return decisions (*departs*). For individuals who have been ordered to leave, the categories include: *éloignements forcés* (forced returns), which also include individuals who are transferred to other EU countries; *éloignements aidés* (assisted voluntary returns), and *éloignements spontanés*, (spontaneous return). These categories map onto Eurostat types of return, and while data publicly available through the Ministry of the Interior⁽¹⁵²⁾ do not match perfectly, they are in line with Eurostat. In contrast, for individuals who have not received an order to leave, the categories include *departs volontaires aidés* (assisted voluntary returns) and *departs spontanés* (spontaneous departure).
- In **Italy**, the last data on assisted voluntary return dates back to 2022, as no programmes were active in 2023⁽¹⁵³⁾. Data originates from the Ministry of the Interior, and while not publicly available can be retrieved in official reports⁽¹⁵⁴⁾. These reports categorise forced return operations based on two

(151) Eurostat, Third-country nationals returned following an order to leave - annual or quarterly data (rounded) [migr_eirtn, migr_eirtn1] and Third-country nationals who have left the territory by type of return and citizenship [migr_eirt_vol].

(152) Ministère de l'Intérieur - Direction Générale des Étrangers en France (n.d.).

(153) As of 2024, the Italian Ministry of the Interior signed launched a new Assisted Voluntary Return project to be implemented by the IOM and spanning over three years. The project should primarily target nationals from specific countries, including Bangladesh, Pakistan, Nigeria, Egypt, Tunisia, Morocco, and Côte d'Ivoire. See: EMN (2023) and IOM (2024). In addition, Frontex supports assisted voluntary returns in Italy through the EU Reintegration Programme (EURP). See: Frontex (n.d.).

(154) For example: Corte dei Conti (2022); Garante Nazionale dei Diritti delle Persone Private della Libertà personale (n.d.).

key factors: the method of execution, which includes charter flights, escorted returns, and non-escorted returns, and the type of procedure implemented, such as judicial expulsions, ministerial expulsions, and public security expulsions, as well as deferred refusal of entry issued by the Police (Questura – as seen in 3.1.1.1, these are not the consequence of a return decision in line with the Return Directive).

- In **Spain**, data on returns is not publicly available, but can be accessed following requests through the transparency registry⁽¹⁵⁵⁾ to the Ministry of the Interior. Data is disaggregated into returns (*expulsiones*), summary returns (*devoluciones* – see Section 3.11) and readmissions (*readmisiones* – returns in the framework of readmission agreements). Both returns and summary returns are included in Eurostat’s (*migr_eirtn*), even if the latter are not linked to return decisions⁽¹⁵⁶⁾.
- In **Germany**, national data covers forced returns (*Abschiebung*) and returns of persons whose departure was assisted by the “Bund-Länder-Rückkehrförderprogramm REAG/GARP” (reintegration and emigration programme for asylum seekers in Germany / government assisted repatriation programme)⁽¹⁵⁷⁾. There are also programmes managed by Länder but data are not available in a single repository. Considering the lack of information available on Eurostat on voluntary returns (whereby all return result as forced returns), national data are an essential element to complement the analysis on the pathways outside irregularity.

In the five Member States the International Organisation for Migration has been a key stakeholder in implementing assisted voluntary return programmes, and data on beneficiaries can also be retrieved through its channels⁽¹⁵⁸⁾.

3.3.2 Access to a residence permit or authorisation to stay

The postponement of return decisions may result in tolerated stay or temporary permits allowing the TCN to remain in a Member State’s territory while obstacles to return persist. In some Member States, these types of temporary authorisation or toleration can also pave the way towards more stable forms of residence, that remove the obligation to leave. In other cases, residence permits or authorisations are directly accessible to persons staying irregularly (Section 3.2.2, Figure 10). Access requirements vary across Member States, but they have often been linked to the TCN’s engagement in labour or their integration in the host Member State. The following sections examine practices for the issuing residence permits or authorisations to irregularly staying TCNs and the data landscape across the five case studies.

3.3.2.1 National practices

- In **Germany** and **Austria**⁽¹⁵⁹⁾, permits or authorisations are available either following an initial toleration period, or to TCNs who have not been issued a *Duldung* but cannot be returned, and are generally granted on humanitarian, family or integration grounds.
 - In **Austria**, these mechanisms are grouped under the notion of “**residence permits issued for exceptional circumstances**”⁽¹⁶⁰⁾. These can take the form of the so-called “residence permit plus”, the “standard residence permit”, and “the residence permit for special protection” (see Annex 1 for a full description). The permits are issued on family, integration, or humanitarian grounds for a period of twelve months (only the “residence permit for special protection” is renewable), and allow access to a more stable

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(155) Administracion General del Estado (n.d.).

(156) Policia Nacional (n.d.).

(157) Mediendienst Integration (2024c).

(158) The IOM’s Migration Data Portal includes statistics on assisted return by host country, updated as of 2023.

(159) Kraler, A. (2009).

(160) The legal requirements are set out in detail in Article. 54 et seqq. of the Asylum Act 2005, under Residence Permits for Exceptional Circumstances. See Stiller, M. and Humer, L. (2020); Bassermann, M. A (2019); Hinterberger, K. F. (2023).

form of residence permit (the “Red-White-Red Card plus”) afterwards⁽¹⁶¹⁾.

- In **Germany**, regional authorities (*Länder*) can issue different types of residence permits to TCNs who have an obligation to return. These permits, governed by the German Residence

Act, are issued on humanitarian or personal grounds, in cases of long-lasting obstacles to return, or following demonstrated integration in Germany. In 2022, new legislation was introduced opening a new pathway to allow long-term *Duldung*-holders to regularise their stay (Box 18).

Box 18. Access to residence permits in Germany.

The Land authorities, pending approval of the Ministry of Interior, can issue residence permits to specific TCNs. This has been used to grant residence right to those whose return had been suspended for years. There are several grounds on the basis of which a person with an order to leave (suspended or enforceable) can receive a permit⁽¹⁶²⁾. In particular:

- **Humanitarian grounds:** the Land authorities may grant humanitarian permits to people enforceably required to leave, for humanitarian or personal grounds, or for public interest reasons. The assessment is always on a case-by-case basis, and a permit may be granted when the repatriation would constitute an exceptional hardship for the foreigner⁽¹⁶³⁾. In addition, the Lander have hardships commissions that may petition the supreme land authority to issue a residence title on humanitarian reasons or personal grounds⁽¹⁶⁴⁾.
- **Persisting obstacles:** 18 months after the suspension of the deportation, and if the obstacles to deportation are not the person’s fault, the Land authorities may grant a permit to people who are enforceably required to leave but whose departure is not possible by law or practical obstacles, and the obstacles do not seem to be removable in the foreseeable future⁽¹⁶⁵⁾.
- **Integration of minors and young adults:** persons aged 14-21 whose deportation has been suspended may be granted a residence permit if they are well-integrated. To assess the integration, the following conditions must be met: the person should have resided in Germany without interruption for the past 4 years, have attended school in Germany for a period of 4 years or has acquired a final certificate, and show signs that integration will be successful. The parents of minors who have been granted such permit can also be issued a permit⁽¹⁶⁶⁾.
- **Integration of adults:** persons whose deportation has been suspended and who are permanently integrated in Germany are to be granted a residence permit. The requirements include uninterrupted residence for the past 8 years (or 6 if the person lives with a minor), subsistence ensured primarily by pursuing economic activity, sufficient oral command of the German language (A2), children attending school, if present⁽¹⁶⁷⁾.

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(161) In the case of the residence permit for special protection, eligibility for a “red-white-red card plus” is examined ex officio. In other cases, an application for a “red-white-red card plus” must be submitted. Holders of a residence permit on grounds of Art. 8 of the ECHR and of a residence permit on grounds of particularly exceptional cases under the Asylum Act can receive a red-white-red card plus if: a) they have already held a humanitarian residence permit under the Asylum Act for 12 months and have fulfilled Module 1 of the Integration Agreement; or b) if they are employed at the time of the decision and their earnings meet the monthly minimum income threshold.

(162) Sections 23 and 25, Residence Act.

(163) Section 25(4), Residence Act.

(164) Section Section23a, Residence Act. The hardship commissions take actions based only on their own initiative, and the decisions are discretionary.

(165) Section 25(5), Residence Act.

(166) Section 25a(1), 25a(2), Residence Act.

(167) Section 25b, Residence Act.

In late 2022, the ‘**Opportunity Right of Residence**’ (‘Chancen-Aufenthaltsrecht’) law was introduced, aiming at reducing the number of chain tolerations and providing a new pathway towards **permanent residence** (Bundesministerium des Innern und für Heimat, 2022).

The requirements are:

- having been in Germany for at least five years by 31 October 2022 (including time spent with a ‘*Duldung* light’ status);
- having always had a toleration status or a residence permit during that time-period;
- no conviction for an international crime;
- accepting the liberal constitutional order of Germany;
- and not repeatedly providing false information about the own identity and nationality⁽¹⁶⁸⁾.

TCN who meet these requirements may enter an 18-month probation period before becoming eligible for residence. During the probation period, the person should try to meet the requirements for a right to stay⁽¹⁶⁹⁾. If they fail, they will be issued a “*Duldung*” again.

- In Italy, since the 1980s, regularisation of irregularly staying TCNs has mainly taken place through **ad-hoc, large-scale employment-based regularisation programmes** (*sanatorie*).⁽¹⁷⁰⁾ The latest two amnesties date back to 2012 and 2020, and have **primarily targeted domestic and agricultural workers**. In addition, a number of short-term residence permits linked to very exceptional specific circumstances (e.g. violence, exploitation, medical conditions, and judicial reasons) are available to third-country nationals, and may open the path to longer-term regular stay (Annex 5).
- **Spain extensively issues residence permits**

allowing TCNs to exit irregular stay (labelled as ‘temporary residence due to exceptional circumstances’),

regardless of whether they had already received a return decision (Box 19). They are granted in relation to third-country nationals’ integration in the country (*arraigo*), as proved by the past work, family or social connections, education or training, or previous stay on a regular permit (see Annex 5 for the detailed requirements). These permits are also granted on humanitarian grounds⁽¹⁷¹⁾, when cooperation with authorities is needed⁽¹⁷²⁾, or for matters of national security and public interest⁽¹⁷³⁾.

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(168) The law is explained here: <https://www.integrationsbeauftragte.de/ib-de/ich-moechte-mehr-wissen-ueber/chancen-aufenthalt>.

(169) In particular the permits for good integration described in Section 25a and 25b of the Residence Act.

(170) Hendow, M et al (2024); Conte, C et al (2024).

(171) Authorization on humanitarian grounds encompasses various scenarios: individuals who are victims of certain crimes involving aggravated circumstances such as racism, anti-Semitism, or other forms of discrimination as outlined in the Criminal Code; victims of domestic violence (in both cases, a final judicial resolution is necessary); foreigners suffering from a sudden and severe illness requiring specialized treatment unavailable in their home country; and situations where returning to the country of origin to obtain a visa poses a threat to the individual or their family. For more information see EMN (2018).

(172) According to Article 127 of Royal Decree 557/2011: Authorization based on collaboration with public authorities, national security, or public interest pertains to cooperation with administrative, police, and judicial entities. In such cases, these authorities may request the relevant bodies to grant a residence permit to the individual involved. For more information see EMN (2018).

(173) EMN (2018), p.7.

Box 19. Access to residence permits in Spain.

The Spanish *arraigo* (integration or settlement) permits are the most used mechanism in this country, and include different types of permits, each with its own requirements (see Annex 5).

Spain also issues permits on humanitarian grounds, which in recent years has been mainly granted to Venezuelan nationals. In 2023, Almost 90% of asylum applications lodged by **Venezuelan nationals** were registered in Spain. However, the international protection recognition rate for this nationality at the EU level stood at less than 3% in 2023 (and was less than 1% in Spain). The vast majority of applications from this country of origin receive, in fact, humanitarian protection. In Spain, following a resolution by the Ministry of the Interior in 2019, unsuccessful asylum applicants from Venezuela are systematically granted a residence permit. The resolution was implemented retroactively, and applied to all applications lodged after 1 January 2014.

Additionally, a recent decree amending the Law on Foreigners entered into force in May 2025, introducing simplified pathways to access residence permits through training, work, and family reasons. Under the new rules, most permit holders can start working immediately, and a seasonal work permit has been created. Furthermore, a new type of *arraigo* has been introduced (Annex 1)⁽¹⁷⁴⁾. The amendment also establishes that time spent as asylum applicants will no longer count towards the required residence period for obtaining *arraigo*.

- In **France**, the Code of Entry and Residence of Foreigners and of the Right to Asylum (CESEDA) foresees the issuing of residence permits for exceptional reasons (*admission exceptionnelle du séjour*) on the basis of employment or personal/family reasons (see Annex 1 for the requirements). The so-called Valls Circular⁽¹⁷⁵⁾, introduced in 2012, provided prefects with guidance for the examination of residence permit applications, and specified criteria for the issuance of employment-based permits. Under this ministerial act, employers needed to apply for the residence permit of their employees⁽¹⁷⁶⁾. The legal framework underwent significant changes in recent years:

- In 2024, a new immigration law⁽¹⁷⁷⁾ entered into force and introduced a temporary 1-year

permit focused on **sectors of the labour market** considered to be **under pressure**. TCN working in these sectors could apply to temporary permits independently (employers are no longer involved in the application process)⁽¹⁷⁸⁾. The new legislation introduced amendments to the Code of Entry and Residence of Foreigners and of the Right to Asylum, including the possibility to **refuse residence permits to TCNs who failed to comply with return decisions or entry bans**⁽¹⁷⁹⁾.

- Further changes were introduced in January 2025⁽¹⁸⁰⁾ and aligned the issuing on residence permits for exceptional reasons with provisions of the 2024 Immigration Law, including by

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(174) Arraigo de segunda oportunidad (« second chance »).

(175) Circulaire INTK1229185C du 28 novembre 2012.

(176) Infantino, F (2024); Ince Beqo, G. et al (2024), p.37.

(177) Law n. 2024-42 of 26 January 2024.

(178) Entreprenre.Service-Public.fr (2024).

(179) Article 7, Loi n° 2024-42 du 26 janvier 2024.

(180) The changes were introduced by the Retailleau Circular, which repealed the Valls Circular.

encouraging the prioritisation of applications for economic sectors with labour shortages⁽¹⁸¹⁾. The new circular also introduced **stricter requirements**, including signing a “contrat d’engagement”⁽¹⁸²⁾, an assessment of French language proficiency, and 7-year presence in France (increased from 5 years, in the repealed circular).

An overview of the various mechanisms for the issuing of residence permits to irregularly staying TCNs, its main elements and requirements is available in Annex 1.

3.3.2.2 Statistics on residence permits or authorisations to stay

Public availability of data on the number of TCNs accessing residence permits or authorisations varies across Member States.

- Flow data are publicly available in **Austria, France and Spain**, while only stock data is available in **Germany**
 - In **Germany**, the Federal Statistics Office (DESTATIS) publishes statistics on permits disaggregated by the legal grounds upon which these were issued, drawing from the Central Population Register (AZR). While data availability is partially limited, publicly accessible data includes *stock* data up to December 2019 for all third-country nationals registered in the AZR database, and up to 2023 for individuals who have applied for international protection⁽¹⁸³⁾.
 - In **France**, the Ministry of the Interior publishes yearly statistics⁽¹⁸⁴⁾ on residence permits, including

exceptional residence authorisations. Data is disaggregated by the type of authorisation (employment or family based).

- In Spain, data is publicly available through the Ministry of the Interior’s Permanent Observatory for Immigration⁽¹⁸⁵⁾. Consolidated yearly data is available from 2014, and broken down by reason. However, this disaggregation includes “*arraigo*” and “other temporary residence authorisations due to other exceptional circumstances” (which also include permits issued to beneficiaries of international protection)⁽¹⁸⁶⁾, making it difficult to identify the specific grounds upon which the authorisation was issued. Quarterly data, available as of September 2013, does allow to identify the type of *arraigo* granted⁽¹⁸⁷⁾.
- In **Austria**, yearly asylum statistics⁽¹⁸⁸⁾ include a disaggregation on residence permits issued for exceptional circumstances (*Aufenthaltstitel aus berücksichtigungswürdigen Gründen*). Besides the overall number of permits issued, the statistics include the number of positive and negative decisions on applications for these residence permits, and further disaggregate the data by whether the subject of the decision had applied for asylum or not.
- In **Italy**, data on applications to regularisation programmes is scant, but can be traced in documents and reports published by the Ministry of the Interior⁽¹⁸⁹⁾. Data on actual beneficiaries is harder to come by – this may be because the assessment of applications to these programmes usually spans over a number of years. According to civil society sources⁽¹⁹⁰⁾, based on data sourced from requests of access to public information, as

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(181) In the new circular, prefects are asked to prioritize the procedure for regularising undocumented workers in shortage occupations introduced in Law 2024-42. (Article L.435-4), rather than individuals requesting regularisation on humanitarian or family reasons (Article L.435-1).

(182) According to the circular, applications for residence permits for exceptional circumstances, not accompanied by a ‘Contrat d’engagement à respecter les principes de la République’ (a statement of agreement with the basic principles of the French Republic) should be considered incomplete and declared inadmissible.

(183) DESTATIS, Schutzsuchende: Deutschland, Stichtag, Geschlecht, Schutzstatus, Code: 12531-000, <https://www-genesis.destatis.de/datenbank/online/statistic/12531/table/12531-0007>

(184) Ministère de l’Intérieur, Direction General des Étrangers en France (n.d.).

(185) Ministerio de Inclusion, Seguridad Social y Migraciones. Observatorio Permanente de la Inmigración (n.d.).

(186) Ministerio de Inclusion, Seguridad Social y Migraciones, Observatorio Permanente de la Inmigración (n.d.).

(187) Ministerio de Inclusion, Seguridad Social y Migraciones. Observatorio Permanente de la Inmigración (n.d.).

(188) Bundesministerium Inneres, Statistiken (n.d. e).

(189) Ministero dell’Interno (2021).

(190) Ero Straniero (2024).

FIGURE 14. TCNs ordered to leave, returned following an order to leave and granted an authorisation or permit to stay in Austria, France and Spain. Cumulated data 2021-2023⁽¹⁹²⁾

Source: JRC elaboration based on Eurostat [*migr_eiord*], [*migr_eirtn*] and national statistics.

Note: Data for Spain includes temporary residence authorisations for *arraigo*; data for France includes exceptional residence authorisations for family and employment reasons; data for Austria includes positive decisions on permits for exceptional circumstances.

of October 2024 75% applications of the 2020 regularisation programme had been assessed, with a success rate of 59% (130,000 successful applications)⁽¹⁹¹⁾.

A comparative analysis of the latest national statistics against Eurostat data on return decisions and actual returns reveals differences in the use of these types of permits within Member States (Figure 14).

- In France and Austria, the number of TCNs ordered to leave significantly exceeds those who actually returned following an order to leave or accessed a permit or authorisation to stay. In Austria, the number of TCNs ordered to leave is roughly double the number of those who left or obtained a permit, while in France, it is nearly three times higher.

- Conversely, Austria’s returns are more than twice as high as residence permits or authorisations issued, while in France, exceptional authorisations to stay are nearly four times higher than effective returns.

- Spain presents a different situation, where the number of TCNs granted an *arraigo* permit is almost 2.5 times higher than those issued return decisions, and almost 30 times higher than TCNs returned.

- In Italy, the permits granted in the context of the 2020 regularisation from June 2020 as of October 2024 are approximately ten times higher than the actual return in this period⁽¹⁹³⁾.

- In Germany, it is not possible to compare the number of persons returned after an order to leave with the number of persons who accessed a permit after

(191) Migration Policy Institute (2024).

(192) It is important to note that these different datasets do not necessarily correspond to the same target population. E.g. TCN returned following an order to leave in 2021-2023 may have received their return decisions in 2020.

(193) Total returns from quarter 3 2020 to quarter 3 2034 are 13,160. Source: Eurostat, Third-country nationals returned following an order to leave, by type of return, citizenship, country of destination, age and sex - quarterly data.

an irregular status, as for the latter indicator flow data are not available. However, it is possible to compare the number of persons that, at a *given moment in time*, are forcibly required to leave with the number of persons who hold a residence permit among the ones listed in Box 18. At the end of 2023, among the persons who sought protection in Germany, 19,570 were holding a permit for being

permanently integrated (Section 25b of the Residence Act), and 17,870 persons were forcibly required to leave (DESTATIS)⁽¹⁹⁴⁾. At the same time, as of June 2023, the number of persons obliged to leave was 297,098 (of which 224,769 with a tolerated status), while the number of persons holding a residence permit after an irregular status was 128,622⁽¹⁹⁵⁾.

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(194) DESTATIS, Persons seeking protection, code 12531-0007. The numbers reported in the text refer only to persons who sought protection in Germany.

(195) This number includes the following categories of permits: i) permits to people who are enforceably required to leave but whose departure is not possible by law or practical obstacles, and the obstacles do not seem to be removable in the foreseeable future (Section 25(5) of the Residence Act); ii) permits for persons whose deportation has been suspended and who are permanently integrated in Germany (Section 25(b) of the Residence Act); iii) humanitarian permits to people enforcedly required to leave, for humanitarian or personal grounds, or for public interest reasons; iv) Persons aged 14-18 or 18-21 whose deportation has been suspended and are well-integrated; v) persons who are enforceably required to leave but are given a permit by the hardship commissions on humanitarian reasons or personal grounds.

4. Possible solutions

As it emerges from the analysis presented in this report, significant gaps in evidence and data hamper a full understanding of the management of irregularly staying TCNs by Member States. Addressing this issue effectively entails investigating the dynamics of irregular entry and stay, the intersection of asylum and return policies, the efficacy of return procedures and their outcomes, and the mechanisms by which TCNs transit from irregular to regular status, and vice-versa.

The previous chapter highlighted that public EU and national data can be used to investigate these dynamics and to quantify pathways into irregularity only to a limited extent. The available datasets present significant challenges: i) they are often not linked with *individual identification* codes that would allow to follow the same person over time, link information collected separately, and avoid statistical double-counting⁽¹⁹⁶⁾; ii) they are often managed by *different authorities* and respond to *different operational purposes*⁽¹⁹⁷⁾; iii) they do not record the complete information needed to map the trajectories in and out of irregularity⁽¹⁹⁸⁾.

These challenges can be addressed through the collection and analysis of more comprehensive data and information. In particular, two potential solutions could be explored in line with the Migration and Asylum Pact's ambition to digitalise the EU return system and the new data sharing requirements proposed in the new Return Regulation⁽¹⁹⁹⁾:

- the creation of a longitudinal database, built on interlinked datasets, which would enable the tracking of TCN's changes in status over time;
- the design of an irregular migration management dashboard that, even without interlinked datasets,

would allow for some inferences on the pathways in and out of irregularity.

4.1 Interlinked databases

In some Member States, interlinked databases that record the migration history (including any pathways in and out of irregularity) of a single person over time are available. The data collected are not publicly accessible, or accessible only in the form of aggregated extracts. While these databases serve the primary purpose of supporting case management, the data collected can be used also for statistical purposes. Germany and Austria offer good examples.

The **Central Register of Foreigners - AZR** in Germany is a comprehensive database that stores personal records of TCNs who have been in the country for more than three months or who apply for asylum. It is administered by the German Federal Office for Migration and Refugees (Bundesamt für Migration und Flüchtlinge - BAMF) and can be accessed by various authorities on all administrative levels. It contains information on the individual's legal status, the arrival, residency status, work permits, age, gender, education and address. Regarding the legal status, the AZR shows whether a person is authorised to stay (e.g. with a refugee status), received a permit, was ordered to leave, had their removal suspended, or receives a toleration status). It also registers whether a person left Germany and received return assistance (Hammerl/Janik, 2021).

The AZR data is stored in a historicised manner, meaning that it represents the stock of persons with a specific legal status at each given point in time. As such, it

(196) For example, the dataset on asylum decisions is not linked with the dataset on orders to leave in Eurostat.

(197) For instance, the dataset on interceptions of persons irregularly entering the territory is often managed by police authorities, while the dataset of asylum decisions is managed by asylum authorities.

(198) For instance, datasets on order to leave do not distinguish between suspended or active ones, or data on residence permits do not distinguish whether the TCN had an irregular status.

(199) The proposal contains important provisions on statistics (Article 48), which would make compulsory for the Member States to share with Eurostat data on TCNs subject to: recognized return decisions issued by other Member States; subject to alternative to detention; and subject to detention. Member States would also have to share with Frontex, for each third country, the number of: readmission applications submitted; requests for confirmation of nationalities and relative replies received; requests for issuance travel documents, relative replies, and travel document issued; and beneficiaries of reintegration assistance.

FIGURE 15. Peitz (2025) analysis on cumulative incidence of competing pathways out of irregularity.

Source: Source: Peitz, L. (2025). Analysis based on AZR data (2013-2022) on 412,226 irregular stays after final rejection.

represents a valuable resource for longitudinal analysis and provides insights into pathways in and out of irregularity. It significantly improves the evidence base on the management of irregular migration and return. However, it is essential to note that the data may not always be reliable (Box20).

AZR is not publicly accessible⁽²⁰⁰⁾ but various sources, e.g. the German Statistical Office – DESTATIS, Parliamentary enquiries, and general studies (e.g. by the European Migration Network), publish data drawn from it⁽²⁰¹⁾.

A recent example is a study by the BAMF⁽²⁰²⁾ that investigates the *pathways out* of irregularity of rejected asylum seekers over time, and assesses the probability for each nationality of asylum applicant to return voluntarily, forcibly, or to receive a residence permit as it changes over time⁽²⁰³⁾. The study shows that over

the analysed 9-year period, the likelihood for rejected asylum applicants at final instance to return voluntarily or to receive a residence permit are similar (between 34 and 38%), while the likelihood to return forcibly is much lower (10%) (Figure 15). The likelihood to return (forcibly or voluntarily) does not significantly increase two or three years after the asylum rejection, while the likelihood of accessing a residence permit gradually increases over time.

In principle, AZR data would allow to investigate also *pathways into* irregularity (e.g. asylum rejection at first instance, overstay of a permit, early termination of the allowed stay); the relationship between the various instances of the asylum procedure and return decisions, and their possible suspension; as well as changes in the stock and flow of persons obliged to leave or with a suspended return decision.

(200) That said, research institutions can request access to an anonymised sample of the data via the BAMF- Research Data Centre (<https://www.bamf.de/EN/Themen/Forschung/Forschungsdatenzentrum/forschungsdatenzentrum-node.html>) and general overview figures are accessible via GENESIS-Online, a database of the German Federal Statistical Office: <https://www-genesis.destatis.de/genesis/online>; <https://www-genesis.destatis.de/datenbank/online/statistic/12521/table/12521-0007/table-toolbar/search/s/ZHVvZHVuZW==>.

(201) It should be noted that, when data are reported across these sources, numbers often do not match. This may be due to the fact that AZR is accessed at different points in time, and that different filters are applied (e.g. restricting the extract only to asylum applicants, or selecting only some categories of Duldung).

(202) Peitz, L. (2023).

(203) Another study using a longitudinal approach to investigate return patterns in the case of the Netherlands is Leerkes et al. (2014). The authors use a combination of data from the Immigration and Naturalisation Service (Immigratie and Naturalisatie Dienst or IND), the International Organization for Migration (IOM) Netherlands, and the Repatriation and Departure Service (Dienst Terugkeer & Vertrek or DT&V). The study identifies return patterns of rejected asylum seekers, adopting a cohort analysis approach, where the return behaviour of rejected asylum seekers is followed over time.

Box 20. Quality issues affecting the reliability of the AZR for statistical purposes.

Notwithstanding its potential, there are several issues affecting the reliability of AZR:

- The BAMF, local and central foreigners' authorities can all access AZR and input records. Hence, issues arise concerning the lack of harmonisation between these authorities in terms of definitions and reporting practices, especially on the use of the specific legal categories. The information on the legal status of foreigners, for instance, is fragmented into almost 200 different categories based on the existing legal provisions. This makes it difficult to share and compare this data beyond Germany (notably with Eurostat). This is an issue particularly critical for orders to leave. Not only the legal obligation to leave can be due to different reasons. In the AZR, there are 22 sub-categories referring to suspension of deportation. On asylum rejections, only recently AZR started recording both final and first instance decisions, while before it contained information only on the final rejection.
- The data can be outdated, overwritten, incomplete or faulty due to data entry mistakes and lack of updating (Rietig and Günnewig, 2020: 13). The German statistical office (Destatis) has concluded that there are about one million AZR entries on foreigners with invalid or no data on their legal authorisation to stay in Germany. This is partially connected to the high number of migrants, especially asylum seekers, crossing the border into Germany between 2015 and 2016, during the so called "refugee crisis"⁽²⁰⁴⁾.
- Even though foreigners are expected to report their departure and notify the authorities, they rarely do so. There are only few incentives for complying with such requirement. In addition, authorities do not check in a systematic manner whether a person actually leaves. This can result in an under reporting of people who actually left. This situation makes it difficult for practitioners to understand, and even estimate, the actual number of people who should return or be returned at a given moment in time (Destatis, 2023: 8). Within the AZR, there is the option to record that a person moved to an unknown location ('Fortzug nach Unbekannt'), if a person cannot be traced anywhere. However, there is no indication whether this is to a spontaneous return, or because a person absconded. If a person can be traced again after some time, they are removed from the unknown location category and registered again within the AZR (cf. Peitz, 2023: 7)⁽²⁰⁵⁾.

In Austria, the Federal Office for Immigration and Asylum developed a central IT application called Integrated Administration of Aliens system (**Integrierte Fremdenadministration – IFA**)⁽²⁰⁶⁾. Since 2014, IFA progressively streamlined the asylum and immigration applications previously managed separately within the Ministry of Interior. The IFA contains unique identifiers and is connected to the Austrian Central Population Register. The system enables cross-checks of visa information with data on residence and basic services provided to asylum applicants. It allows automatic updates on residence status on a daily basis, ensuring that the list of persons with an obligation to leave

is consistently up to date. It is also possible to book seats on return charter flights directly from the list⁽²⁰⁷⁾. IFA also allows to store documentation related to the removal process, filter it by country of origin, and record the expiration dates of the confirmations of nationality by third countries (which are necessary to obtain travel documents for the TCN).

In the light of the evidence collected in this report, including the examples described above, the suggested **roadmap for the creation of longitudinal databases** would include the following steps:

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(204) Other data challenges arise in relation to the Covid-19 pandemic and Brexit resulting in flawed or missing information on foreigners who entered in a short period of time in Germany (Ibid.: 7f.).

(205) The authors of the German case study were unable to verify if or how this change is shared with Eurostat.

(206) Stiller, M. (2020).

(207) Stiller, M. (2020).

- *Assessment of the baseline.* **Aim:** to identify Member States with longitudinal and interlinked databases already in place in the return, asylum, visa, border management and regular migration systems. **How:** via survey sent to Member States.
- *Analysis of the existing databases.* **Aim:** to design and pilot comparative analyses that would build and elaborate on the model adopted by BAMF (Peitz 2023). **How:** the Commission could work with the group of Member States with longitudinal and interlinked databases.
- *Identification of the opportunities and constraints.* **Aim:** to identify potential technological solutions (e.g. blockchain), policy developments (e.g. the Central Repository for Reporting and Statistics building on the EU large-scale IT systems), the requirements for such databases, as well as the existing obstacles in different Member States. **How:** technical study carried out by a committee of experts, including aspects of treatment of personal data, as well as anonymisation practices for analytical purposes.
- *Mutual learning and funding opportunities.* **Aim:** to capitalise on the experience of Member States with more advanced data landscapes and procedures, and create economies of scale. **How:** targeted funding made available at EU level and with joint procurement.

4.2 Irregular migration management dashboard

The findings of the case studies contribute to **refining the map of irregularity pathways** presented in Chapter 2 along the following lines:

- In some cases, more informative data sources are available at national level;
- Some Member States adopt forms of toleration status, which entail a suspension of return procedures, and may work as a bridge towards residence permits, i.e. pathways out of irregularity;
- The pathways out of irregularity, whether by means of return or access to a regular permit, do not always encompass formal return procedures (and the issuance of a return decision).

Figure 16 illustrates the revised map of irregularity pathways as it was presented in Figure 2. The revised map contributes to conceptualise the development of an **irregular migration management dashboard** that details, for each dimension of the pathways, the practices, the data sources, and actual numerical values.

Such dashboard would allow to integrate all the available information of how irregular migration is managed in each Member State. National data would still not be immediately comparable across Member States. However, it would be possible to identify, in each Member State, the relative magnitude of each pathway in and out of irregularity, hence providing a more thorough overview and a finer assessment of return effectiveness.

The Table in Annex 6 lists the elements that the dashboard could contain, as well as the analysis that would be feasible on these elements (with the relevant indicators to consider). A dashboard would facilitate the visualisation of the table's elements, and comparisons across Member States.

The **roadmap to the dashboard** would include the following steps:

- *Validation of the pathways into and out of irregularity with all Member States.* **Aim:** to further refine the map of irregularity pathways, which relies on the report's five case studies and needs integration from the practices of other Member States. **How:** a participatory workshop with Member States' representatives.
- *Collection of official information from Member States.* **Aim:** to progress from the exploratory phase, be actionable and vetted for the policy context. The case studies of this report were explorative and aimed at identifying the main dimensions of irregularity. After validating the map, information gathering from Member States needs to be more targeted and systematic than in the current study, based on desk research and interviews. **How:** official information collected by the Commission, by sending a targeted questionnaire to the national administrations.
- *Refinement of the components of the irregular migration dashboard.* **Aim:** integrating in the table describing the main elements of the dashboard the answers to the questionnaires. **How:** review of the table on the basis of the survey.

FIGURE 16. Revised map of irregularity pathways..

○ Managing irregular migration and return

- *Design and implementation of the irregular migration management dashboard.* **Aim:** to make the relevant information immediately understandable, visually appealing; to showcase straightforwardly any critical element, e.g. data gaps; to identify the relative size of each pathway with colour coding; and to couple the data with information on the practices, thus shedding significant light on their interpretation. **How:** involvement of targeted expertise on design dashboards or scoreboard; integration in a web-portal, e.g. the KCMD website.
- *Update of the dashboard.* **Aim:** to ensure timely feeding of data and information, and secure the operability of the tool for policy-makers. **How:** annual circulation of the targeted questionnaire to the Member States and dashboard update.

5. Conclusions

Assessing the management of irregular migration: challenges and data gaps

- The availability of timely, harmonised, good quality data and information is essential to monitor the performance of a policy, and to assess its effectiveness. In the area of return policy, and more generally in the management of irregularly staying TCNs, the data and information landscape needs substantial improvement.
- At EU level, Eurostat collects statistics on the enforcement of immigration legislation, including data on orders to leave, returns and TCNs found to be illegally present. These indicators are valuable. However, they are insufficient to provide a detailed and comprehensive picture of the functioning of the return system in the EU, and to build meaningful indicators to measure return effectiveness.
- Currently available EU-level data leave a series of questions unanswered. These include: How many TCNs who received a return decision got access to a legal status prior to the completion of return procedures? How many TCNs are supposed to return because they have an enforceable return decision? How many TCNs abscond during the return procedure or move to other EU countries?
- The fragmented data landscape reflects both legal and practical constraints. Return is one element of the broader toolbox that deals with the presence of irregular TCNs. Collecting data and information on how return procedures interact with the other components of irregular migration management is essential. This is particularly important in light of the upcoming implementation of the Pact on Migration and Asylum, which includes effective returns among the core pillars of an effective migration and asylum policy⁽²⁰⁸⁾. The Pact, together with the recently proposed Regulation establishing a common system for the return of TCNs staying irregularly in the Union, may address some gaps by bringing asylum and return procedures closer - for example, by requiring the

simultaneous issue of negative asylum decisions and return decisions (as outlined in Article 37 of the Asylum Procedures Regulation).

- However, EU-level data collection on alternatives to return persist. For example, there is no EU mandate to collect data on TCNs regularising their stay. In addition, the variety of national practices dealing with irregularly staying TCNs complicates the interpretation of single indicators and hampers the possibility of comparative analysis.

Mapping data and practices at the national level

- In the absence of EU-level data, a closer look at the ways in which Member States manage the presence of irregular TCNs can support the monitoring and assessment the EU return policy.
- To better understand the management of irregularly staying TCNs by Member States, it is thus necessary to investigate the dynamics of irregular entry and stay, the intersection of asylum and return policies, the effectiveness of return procedures and their outcomes, and the mechanisms that allow TCNs to transition from irregular to regular status.
- This Science for Policy report provides an initial overview of practices and identifies administrative data (including gaps) for measuring the management of irregularly staying TCNs and return in five selected case studies (Austria, France, Germany, Italy, Spain).

Understanding pathways into irregularity

- Irregular stay can arise from several situations, including entering an EU Member State without proper authorisation, exceeding the allowed visa or visa-exempt period, or having an asylum application rejected. The use of varying definitions and categories at the national level can lead to inconsistent statistical reporting, making it challenging to compare data across EU Member States.

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(208) European Commission (2024), Pact on Migration and Asylum, https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/migration-and-asylum/pact-migration-and-asylum_en

- There is a significant lack of data on individuals who overstay their visas or residence permits. The existing data is often incomplete or inconsistent due to differences in reporting practices and categorisations.
- Member States handle unsuccessful asylum claims and return procedures with a variety of approaches. This further complicates the possibility to quantify and compare data.
- Improving harmonisation and extending data collection to these categories could help address some of these challenges by establishing common definitions and enhancing comparability across Member States.

The complexity of tracking return decisions and their enforcement

- The Return Directive imposes an obligation to Member States to issue return decisions to TNCs identified as illegally staying within their territories. This obligation is implemented in different ways across Member States. Data on the enforceability of return decisions is often incomplete and inconsistent.
- At the EU level, Eurostat data on “third-country nationals ordered to leave” measures the number of administrative or judicial return decisions issued in a given year. However, the enforceability of these decisions can be complex and change over time. For instance, return decisions could be temporarily suspended due to appeals, or there may be legal or practical barriers to their enforcement, such as non-refoulement concerns.
- As a result, it is challenging to accurately estimate the number of TCNs with an active obligation to leave at any given time by simply looking at the return rate. The dynamic nature of these decisions and the various factors that can influence their enforcement make it difficult to determine the true number of individuals who are currently required to leave.

Pathways out of irregularity: return, regularisation and intermediate statuses

- Pursuant to the Return Directive, once the period for voluntary departure has expired (or if no such period was

granted, e.g., due to a risk of absconding), EU Member States are required to take all necessary steps to enforce the return decision, prioritising voluntary return.

- Tolerated stay statuses, granted on legal or practical grounds, complicate the assessment of return effectiveness, as they may allow individuals to remain in the country despite being subject to a return decision.
- Crucially, the grounds on which tolerated stay statuses are granted, their relationship with orders to leave and negative asylum decisions, and the possibility to convert into other permits is not directly comparable across Member States. There are no EU-level statistics on the issuance of tolerated stay permits.
- The use of detention as a measure of last resort for enforcing return decisions is also subject to different national practices and limitations. Data on the use of pre-removal detention and alternatives to detention is scant. This obstructs a thorough assessment of the effectiveness of these measures in return procedures.
- Alternatives to return are not regulated at the EU level, resulting in diverse procedures implemented by individual Member States, leading to different forms of authorisation to stay and regularisation⁽²⁰⁹⁾. However, a significant knowledge gap exists due to the lack of EU-level data on different forms of authorisation and regularisations. This limitation hinders a thorough understanding of how return proceedings intersect with other policy approaches to managing irregularly staying TCNs.

Digital tools for a more effective management of irregular migration

- This Science for Policy report articulates two actionable technical solutions in line with the ambition of the Pact’s to digitalise the EU Return System: 1) the creation of a longitudinal database, which would enable the tracking of TCNs’ change of status over time, and 2) an irregular migration and return dashboard that, even without linked datasets across different statuses, would allow for some inferences, providing valuable insights into the complexities of irregular migration and informing more effective policy responses.

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(209) In most cases, eligibility for regularisation is tied to employment or successful proof of integration into the host country.

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List of abbreviations and definitions

Abbreviations

Definitions

AMMR	Asylum and Migration Management Regulation
AZR	Central Register of Foreigners (Germany)
BAMF	Federal Office for Migration and Refugees (Germany)
BFA	Federal Office for Immigration and Asylum (Austria)
CSO	Civil Society Organisation
DESTATIS	German Statistical Office
EES	Entry-Exit System
EMN	European Migration Network
ESTAT	Eurostat
EU	European Union
EUAA	European Union Agency for Asylum
FRAN	Frontex Risk Analysis Network
Frontex	European Border and Coast Guard Agency
IFA	Integrated Administration of Aliens Systems (Austria)
ISMU	Initiatives and Studies on Multi-ethnicity
IRMA	Integrated Return Management Application
JRC	Joint Research Centre
MIRREM	Measuring Irregular Migration
MS	Member State
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
OTL	Order to Leave
OQTF	Obligation to Leave French Territory
RECAMAS	Return Case Management System
SIS	Schengen Information System
VIS	Visa Information System

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Annexes

Annex 1. Estimates of irregular migrants

The ongoing Horizon Europe Project MirreM⁽²¹⁰⁾ (Measuring irregular migration and related policies) has developed a **conceptual framework for identifying different categories of TCN in an irregular situation, with the primary aim of estimating and quantifying that population**. Building on the approach previously defined by the EU-funded Clandestino project, it defines irregular residents in the EU context as TCN without any legal residence status in the country they are residing in, as well as TCN possessing an authorisation of some sort to remain in the territory but who could be issued an order to leave because of their activities (e.g. visa-exempt citizens engaging in work, students working more than allowed or persons with falsified documents). It also defines ‘quasi-irregularity’ as the situation of individuals who have “tolerated” status (i.e. irregular but for whom the return to their country of origin is not possible for legal or practical reasons)⁽²¹¹⁾.

The project provides a typology of pathways into and out of irregularity and related mechanisms, that is, of ways how TCN become or cease to be in an irregular situation.

- **Pathways into irregularity:** they may include *demographic inflows* (e.g. the children of irregular TCN who cannot obtain regular status), *geographic inflows* (e.g., TCN crossing the EU external border irregularly or refused entry because of lack of necessary documents), as well as *status-related inflows* (e.g. overstaying the duration of a visa or residence permit, or the withdrawal of a residence status).
- **Pathways out of irregularity:** individuals may exit a situation of irregularity due to different circumstances, which include *demographic outflows* (e.g. deaths), geographical outflows (people may leave the territory of a state, either in the context of a return procedure or outside of it, for instance if they were never in

contact with the authorities or when no obligation to leave was issued), or *status-related outflows* (people may experience a change of status after receiving a permit of stay or because they applied for international protection

Techniques estimating the stock of irregularly staying third-country nationals have been tested across the Member States under analysis. In general, estimates can be drawn from datasets that are supposed to capture the entire population, without distinguishing the regular/irregular status, e.g. hospitalisation, death statistics, crime statistics, labour inspections.

In the case studies analysed, estimates of irregularly staying TCN exist in the academic literature or in the policy context.

- Crime statistics have been used to estimate irregularly staying TCN in both **Austria** and **Germany**. In Austria, two approaches have been used for some time, based on a method developed in the Clandestino project. The core concept underlying this estimate is to extrapolate the proportion of irregular TCN in the total population, based on their representation among crime suspects, assuming that the former is equivalent to the latter. Statistics Austria has used a similar method to estimate the number of non-registered foreign nationals in the population register, but has included EU nationals in this number.
- In **France**, data on the use of emergency medical services can be used to provide estimates of the irregularly staying population⁽²¹²⁾. However, this measure is generally considered unreliable due to the fact that only irregularly staying third-country nationals fulfilling very specific conditions can access these services (for example, irregular TCN need to prove their identity and the stability of their residence in France by showing an entry visa or a bill and, in

(210) <https://irregularmigration.eu/> and upcoming Handbook on Irregular Migration Data.

(211) Albert Kraier (UWK) & Jill Ahrens (UWK), Conceptualising Migrant Irregularity for Measurement Purposes, Mirrem Working Paper 2/2023.

(212) Cour des Comptes (2024), La politique de lutte contre l’immigration irrégulière. Claude Evin, Patrick Stefanini, Rapport sur l’aide médicale d’État

FIGURE 17. MirreM estimates on irregular migration stock, minimum and maximum.

Source: [Data Portal – MirreM](#)

some cases, are asked to provide a tax statement or a renting statement).

- In **Spain**, estimates are facilitated by the fact that this country mandates that all residents, regular or irregular, to register in the Padrón (local population registry) in the municipality where they reside. By subtracting data on third-country nationals who have a residence permit from the Padrón, it is possible to estimate the irregularly staying population. However, there are inaccuracies to this method given that specific categories of third-country nationals are not included in statistics on residence permits (e.g., students or applicants for asylum) and because it is possible that persons who obtain EU citizenship do not change their status in the local population registry.

- In **Italy**, the ISMU Foundation, a research institution, has been making indirect estimations of irregular migration since 1991. ISMU estimates emerge from surveys implemented through their Centre Sampling technique. This approach relies on the fact that TCN typically require access to an “aggregation centre” where they can fulfil various essential needs, including socializing, receiving healthcare, practicing religion, enjoying leisure activities, or simply meeting everyday needs.

Recently, MirreM has produced estimates of the irregular migrant stock for the countries described in this report (Kierans, Denis, et al 2024)⁽²¹³⁾ as shown in Figure 17.

(213) Available at <https://irregularmigration.eu/data-portal/#map>

Annex 2. Obligation to leave in national legislation.

Member State	Definition	Target group	Issuing authority
Austria	Rückkehrentscheidung (return decision)	All third-country nationals identified as irregularly staying. In particular, on the basis of three cases: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Negative decision on an application for international protection Determination of irregular stay Withdrawal of an international protection status 	Federal Office for Immigration and Asylum (BFA)
	Obligation de Quitter le Territoire Français (obligation to leave French territory)	All third-country nationals identified as irregularly staying	Prefecture
Germany	Ausreisepflicht (obligation to leave)	Third-country nationals who do not have or no longer have right of residence, including those who are subject of Dublin procedures.	
	Abschiebungsandrohung/ Androhung der Abschiebung (deportation warning)	Third-country nationals identified as irregularly staying. Rejected asylum applicants.	Federal authorities Asylum authority
	Abschiebungsanordnung (deportation order)	Third-country nationals suspected of posing threat to public order or national security.	Federal authorities or Ministry of the Interior
Italy	Attestazione dell'obbligo di rimpatrio (statement of the obligation to return)	Rejected asylum applicants.	Asylum authority
	Decreto d'espulsione - espulsione amministrativa (Administrative return decision)	Third-country nationals found to be irregularly present. Third-country nationals suspected of posing threat to public order or national security.	Prefecture Ministry of the Interior
	Decreto d'espulsione - espulsione giudiziaria (Judicial return decisions)	Third-country nationals convicted with sentences that carry mandatory prison terms and who may pose a security threat. Third-country nationals with final convictions serving the last 2 years of their sentences. Third-country nationals charged with crimes which carry prison terms of less than 2-years. Third-country nationals convicted of irregular entry or stay, as an alternative to a pecuniary fine.	Judicial authorities
	Salida obligatoria (order to leave)	All third-country nationals identified as irregularly staying.	Police authorities
Spain	Orden de expulsión (return decision)	Third-country who fail to comply with orders to leave.	Police authorities Delegated and Sub-delegated authorities.

Source: JRC elaboration based on country analysis.

Annex 3. Status of the order to leave and asylum decisions for selected nationalities in Germany

The table below reports the number of persons with an obligation to leave and related statuses as of 30 June 2023. The source is the Parliamentary enquiry (Document 20/8182), which is based on AZR data.

Nationalities (total and top)	Persons subject to an obligation to leave at the cut-off date of 30 June 2023	Persons subject to an obligation to leave with acquiescence Duldung on 30 June 2023	% of person obligated to leave with Duldung (own calculation)	Persons subject to an obligation to leave with a pending asylum procedure at the cut-off date of 30 June 2023	% of person obligated to leave with pending asylum (own calculation)	Persons subject to an obligation to leave with refused asylum as at the cut-off date of 30 June 2023	% of person obligated to leave with rejected asylum	Persons subject to an obligation to leave with refused asylum without acquiescence at the cut-off date of 30 June 2023	% of rejected asylum obliged to leave without Duldung (own calculation)
Total nationalities	279,098	224,768	81%	33,283	12%	169,907	61%	21,004	12%
Iraq	30,931	27,954	90%	3,303	11%	24,734	80%	2,000	8%
Afghanistan	19,061	16,067	84%	3,976	21%	10,423	55%	887	9%
Nigeria	15,508	14,110	91%	1,722	11%	11,600	75%	931	8%
Russian Federation	15,438	13,432	87%	2,371	15%	10,546	68%	1,105	10%
Türkiye	13,065	10,130	78%	2,175	17%	6,458	49%	1,200	19%
Iran	11,088	9,839	89%	1,841	17%	7,777	70%	704	9%
Syria	10,703	8,329	78%	2,696	25%	n.a.	n.a.	419	n.a.
Serbia	10,653	8,456	79%	977	9%	6,025	57%	1,211	20%
Georgia	7,798	5,254	67%	1,798	23%	4,349	56%	1,113	26%
North Macedonia	7,292	5,586	77%	1,551	21%	3,904	54%	844	22%
Unexplained	7,245	6,625	91%	536	7%	4,557	63%	n.a.	n.a.
Pakistan	6,884	5,962	87%	623	9%	5,404	79%	550	10%
Albania	6,527	n.a.	n.a.	593	9%	n.a.	n.a.	881	n.a.
Lebanon	5,785	5,302	92%	n.a.	n.a.	4,174	72%	n.a.	n.a.
Guinea	5,504	5,123	93%	n.a.	n.a.	3,867	70%	n.a.	n.a.

Annex 4. Tolerated stay statuses and temporary residence permits

Member State	Denomination	Criteria	Duration	Renewal	Conversion
Austria	<i>Duldung</i> (tolerated stay status)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-refoulement; • Withdrawal of international protection, but return is not possible due to the situation in the country of origin; • When return would impose a violation of the right to respect for private and family life; • Practical obstacles to removal for which the person concerned is not responsible (e.g. lack of cooperation from third countries' authorities) 	12 months	Yes, as long as the holder continues to meet the requirements for tolerated stay	Yes (residence titles for 'exceptional circumstances', Articles 55-57 Asylum Act)
France	No tolerated stay status				
Germany	<i>Duldung</i> (tolerated stay status)	According to Section 60a of the Residence Act, the grounds for issuing <i>Duldung</i> are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • reasons related to international law, humanitarian grounds, or for political interests; • removal is impossible by law or practice and no residence permit is granted; • the person is involved in criminal proceedings that require his or her presence; • there are urgent humanitarian or personal grounds or substantial public interest; • the procedure for the acknowledgement of the paternity is suspended ; • the deportation or removal has failed; • the person is a parent or has the custody of a minor with a residence permit; • the person has an illness that might interfere with deportation; 	Variable	Yes	Yes
	<i>Duldung light</i> (§60b AufenthaltG)	For persons without a verified identity who do not support the authorities in the identification process. It does not allow to work and restricts freedom of movement within Germany	?	?	Yes, if under the new Opportunity Residence Act
	<i>AusbildungsDuldung</i> (toleration for training purposes §60c AufenthaltG)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Persons starting a vocational training in a regulated occupation, or starting a training as assistant or helper in a regulated profession that may lead to vocational training in an occupation where shortages exist. • Persons whose asylum applications were rejected • Persons who were already on a <i>Duldung</i> for 3 months and whose identify has been verified. 	3 years + potentially 2 years after vocational training	?	Yes
	<i>BeschäftigungsDuldung</i> (toleration for employment purposes)	for persons (and by extension, their spouses and unmarried children) who entered Germany before 2018, whose identify has been verified (or the person has cooperated in the process, even if unsuccessful), who had a <i>Duldung</i> for the past 12 months, and who were in employment for the past 18 months (Residence Act, Section 60d). In addition, the employment should ensure the subsistence of the person, who has to show at least elementary command of the German language, and no criminal convictions or links to terrorist organisations.	30 months	?	Yes

Italy	<i>Protezione speciale</i> (special protection)	Rejected asylum applicants who cannot be returned on non-refoulement grounds. Permit holders are allowed to engage in work activities	2 years	Yes	No
	Permesso di soggiorno per casi speciali – cure mediche (residence permit for special case 0 – medical care).	Persons with particularly serious health conditions which would not be treated in the country of origin	Duration varies according to a certification of a health provider	Yes	No
	<i>Permesso di soggiorno per casi speciali – disastri naturali</i> (residence permit for special cases – natural disaster).	Issued when the country to which the foreigner should return is in a situation of contingent and exceptional calamity.	6 months	Yes – once	No
Spain	Tolerated status not defined in national legislation.				

Source: JRC elaboration based on country analysis.

Annex 5. Residence permit or authorisations to stay

Member State	Permit, authorisation or mechanism	Description and requirements
Austria	<i>Aufenthaltstitel aus Gründen des Art. 8 EMRK</i> (Permits issued on the basis of Article 8 of the European Convention Human Rights [ECHR]) ⁽²¹⁴⁾ .	These permits are meant to cover situations where return might infringe on the right to family life. Eligibility criteria include the degree of integration in Austria, ties with countries of origin, criminal records. If an application is approved, the beneficiary may be granted a 'residence permit plus' – which allows for unrestricted labour market access – or a 'standard residence permit' – with restricted labour market access – depending successfully passing integration tests and on the employment situation.
	<i>Aufenthaltstitel in besonders berücksichtigungswürdigen Fällen</i> (Permits for particularly exceptional cases) ⁽²¹⁵⁾	This type of permit grants temporary residence if she/he can show a proof of five years of continuous residence (at least three of which must have been legal). Additional factors considered in the decision are the degree of integration, the legal right of accommodation, sufficient health insurance and regular income. If the application is approved, a beneficiary is granted a 'residence permit plus' or a 'standard residence permit' subject to the same conditions as in the case of permits granted on the basis of Article 8 ECHR (see above).
	<i>Aufenthaltsberechtigung besonderer Schutz</i> (Special protection permits) ⁽²¹⁶⁾	Granted to irregularly staying TCN who are witnesses or victims of human trafficking, transnational prostitution or violence in the family, individuals who had been granted a tolerated status for more than one year. Differently from other residence permits issued for exceptional circumstances, the special protection residence permit can be renewed beyond the initial 12-month period of validity. Additionally, holders of special protection residence permit are not required to apply for a Red-White-Red Card plus ⁽²¹⁷⁾ as their eligibility is assessed <i>ex officio</i> by authorities.

(214) Austria, Asylum Act, Article 55.

(215) Austria, Asylum Act, Article 56.

(216) Austria, Asylum Act, Article 57.

(217) Requirements are: language competence at A2 level, legal entitlement to accommodation, adequate health insurance and that the stay is not a financial burden for the state.

	<p><i>Autorisation exceptionnelle au séjour "vie privée et familiale "</i> (exceptional authorisation to stay – family and private life)</p>	<p>1-year permit issued by the Prefecture to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parents of children enrolled in schooling: whose child has been in education for at least 3 years, including nursery school. • Spouses of regularly residing TCN: who can prove cohabitation with the spouse for 18 months. • TCN who entered France as minors and have turned 18: who can prove school attendance since at least the age of 16, and possibly have dependant family members in France. • TCN who have regularly lived in France for more than 10 years: documentary evidence of residence in France needs to be provided. <p>According to the Retailleau Circular, all applicants for exceptional authorisations must sign a "contrat d'engagement". Additionally, certificates or diplomas attesting French language competences should be required. The circular recommends using 7-year presence in France (rather than 5) as an indicator of integration in the country.</p>
<p>France</p>	<p><i>Autorisation exceptionnelle au séjour "travail"</i> (exceptional authorisation to stay – employment)</p>	<p>The duration of the permit varies according to the type of work contract:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TCN with indefinite work contracts will be issued a 1-year permit. Further renewals will be issued for 4-years. • TCN with fixed-term employment contracts will receive a permit that corresponds to the contract's duration. <p>Requirements vary according to economic sectors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic sectors under labour shortages: TCN who have worked in sectors and geographical areas listed as "under pressure" due to labour shortages for at least 12 non-consecutive months in the past 24 months, who can prove consecutive presence in France for 3 years. • Other economic sectors: TCN who have a contract or employment offer, and can prove 7-year presence in France (as per the Retailleau Circular). <p>According to the Retailleau Circular, all applicants for exceptional authorisations must sign a "contrat d'engagement". Additionally, French language competences may be assessed.</p>
<p>Germany</p>	<p>Permit based on Residence Act, Section 23a</p> <p>Permit based on Residence Act, Section 25(4)</p> <p>Permit based on Residence Act, Section 25(5)</p> <p>Permit based on Section 25a(1), and 25a(2)</p> <p>Permit based on Residence Act, Section 25b</p>	<p>The Federal Authorities have hardships commissions that may petition the supreme land authority to issue a residence title to a person who is forcibly required to leave on humanitarian reasons or personal grounds.</p> <p>Humanitarian permits issued by Federal Authorities to people required to leave, for humanitarian or personal grounds, or for public interest reasons. This may be granted when return would constitute an exceptional hardship for the foreigner due to special circumstances.</p> <p>Issued by Federal Authorities to persons whose departure is not possible by law or practical obstacles which do not seem to be removable in the foreseeable future.</p> <p>Persons aged 14-18 or 18-21 whose deportation has been suspended may be granted a residence permit if they are well-integrated. The following conditions must be met: the person should have resided in Germany without interruption for the past 4 years, attended school in Germany for a period of 4 years or acquired a final certificate, show signs that integration will be successful. The parents of minors who have been granted this permit can also be issued a permit</p> <p>Persons whose deportation has been suspended and who are permanently integrated in Germany are to be granted a residence permit. Requirements include uninterrupted residence for the past 8 years. Only 6 years are required if the person lives with a minor, has the ability to support oneself financially through employment; has sufficient oral command of the German language (A2); or children attending school.</p>

	Permit based on the <i>Chancen-Aufenthaltsrecht</i> (Opportunity Right of Residence) law – Residence Act, Section 104c	<p>Requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • having been in Germany for at least five years (including time that has been spent with ‘<i>Duldung</i> light’ status); • having always had a toleration status during that time-period; • being well-integrated; • accepting the liberal constitutional order of Germany; • and not providing false information about the own identity and nationality.²³¹ <p>If all these conditions are met, the TCN may enter an 18-month probation period before becoming eligible for a temporary residence right in Germany, under Section 25 a/b of the Residence Act. Should this probationary period be failed, a <i>Duldung</i> will be issued.</p>
Italy	<i>Sanatorie</i>	Ad-hoc, large scale amnesties with varying requirements according to each programme.
	<i>Permesso di soggiorno per casi speciali – protezione sociale</i> (Residence permit for special cases - social protection).	Persons found to be at risk of violence or serious exploitation, and their safety is compromised, particularly due to their refusal to succumb to the demands of a criminal organization or their cooperation with the authorities during a preliminary investigation or trial. These are issued for 6 months, can be renewed and converted into a work or study permit.
	<i>Permesso di soggiorno per casi speciali – vittime di violenza domestica</i> (Residence permit for special cases - victims of domestic violence)	Issued on grounds of domestic violence only if, in the course of investigations or proceedings for offences for which the mandatory arrest in the act of domestic violence is provided for, committed in Italy in connection with domestic violence, situations of violence or abuse against a foreign national are established and there is a real and present danger to his safety as a result of the choice to evade the violence or as a result of the statements made. ²³²
	<i>Permesso di soggiorno per casi speciali – cure mediche (gravidanza)</i> (Residence permit for special cases - medical treatment (pregnancy).	Issued to irregularly staying pregnant women and their husbands, from the moment pregnancy is certified, until 6-months after the birth of the child. Cannot be renewed nor converted into a work permit, but can be converted into a permit for family reasons.
	<i>Permesso di soggiorno per casi speciali – sfruttamento lavorativo</i> (residence permit for special cases - labour exploitation).	Issued to victims of labour exploitation who lodge complaints and cooperate in criminal proceedings against their employers. Issued for 6 months, renewable for up to 1 year, and can be converted into a work or study permit.
	<i>Permesso di soggiorno per motivi di giustizia</i> (Residence permit for judicial reasons)	Issued when the person’s presence in Italy is indispensable for judicial proceedings, for 3 months and are not convertible into a work or study permit.
	<i>Permesso di soggiorno per casi speciali – Atti di particolare valore civile</i> (Residence permit for special cases - acts of particular civil value)	Issued to persons who engaged in acts of particular civil value (e.g., were exposed to danger to save persons from imminent and serious danger, restore public order, participate in arrests of offenders). Issued for 2 years, renewable and convertible into a work or study permit.
Spain	Autorización de residencia temporal por circunstancias excepcionales: Arraigo	
	<i>Arraigo laboral</i>	Requirements: proof of regular or irregular work for at least 6 months full-time or 12 months part-time; 2 years of residence in Spain; clean criminal record.
	<i>Arraigo social</i>	Requirements: 3 consecutive years of residence in Spain; clean criminal record; signed employment contract; family connections; social integration report (not required if sufficient living expenses are demonstrated); suspended job offer conditional to regularization (not common for long-term irregularities over 5 years)
	<i>Arraigo familiar</i> (temporary residence authorisation on family integration grounds)	Requirements: Parent or tutor of a minor with Spanish nationality; oversees Spanish nationality with a disability and living with them; spouse, registered partner or relative of a Spanish national.

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(218) The law is explained here: <https://www.integrationsbeauftragte.de/ib-de/ich-moechte-mehr-wissen-ueber/chancen-aufenthalt>. There is no clear definition as to what “well integrated” means, but it seems to refer to persons with verified identity who have a good command of the German language and are able to earn a living, cf. Bundesministerium des Innern und für Heimat, 2022.

(219) Ministero del Lavoro e delle Politiche Sociali (2022).

<p><i>Arraigo para la formacion</i> (temporary residence authorisation on education/training integration grounds)</p>	<p>Requirements: 2 years of residence in Spain; clean criminal record; agreement to complete an education program leading to certification in a specific job sector with labor shortages.allowing</p>
<p><i>Arraigo de segunda oportunidad</i> (second change for a temporary residence authorisation).</p>	<p>Requirements: applicants must have previously held a residence permit (not granted under exceptional circumstances), and must have failed to renew it within the past two years due to reasons unrelated to public order, security, or public health concerns.</p>
<p>Other types of temporary residence authorisations due to exceptional circumstances</p>	
<p>Humanitarian grounds</p>	<p>There are two possible permits:</p> <p>Regulated by Article 126 of the Royal Decree 557/2011, granting authorisation to stay on humanitarian grounds to victims of specific crimes (included those aggravated by racism, anti-Semitism or other forms of discrimination; or crimes that have taken place in the family environment); individuals with severe health conditions that cannot be treated in their home country; and those who meet the requirements for a temporary residence permit in Spain but cannot return to their home country to initiate the visa application process due to safety concerns for themselves or their family.</p> <p>Regulated by Article 37 of Law 12/2009, and systematically applied to all unsuccessful asylum applicants of Venezuelan</p>
<p>Cooperating with authorities, reasons of national security or public interest.</p>	<p>Granted under Spanish legislation to third-country nationals who, being in an irregular situation and having worked for at least six months in the last year, cooperate with the labour authorities (Article 127 Royal Decree 557/2011), and; when the individual who is in an irregular situation, and is exempted from responsibility, cooperates with the authorities in a case involving organised crime (Article 137 Royal Decree 557/2011).</p>
<p>Female victims of gender-based violence</p>	<p>Women who are in an irregular situation and have filed a complaint for gender-based violence may obtain a residence and work authorisation (Articles 131-134 Foreigners Decree). This can be done as soon as a protection order or a report by the Public Prosecutor has been released. The victims may also request a residence permit for their children. If the criminal procedure ends with a condemnatory sentence, women who have been victims of gender-based violence will obtain a five-year residence permit, which will also be granted to their children. If the procedure results in a non-condemning sentence, the provisional residence permit will no longer be valid.</p>
<p>Victims of human trafficking</p>	<p>Under Articles 140-146 of Royal Decree 557/2011, once identified by the relevant authorities, victims of human trafficking will be offered at least a 30-day reflection period to decide whether to cooperate with the authorities in investigating the crime. The victim can then apply for a residence and work provisional permit. The person might later apply for a five-year residence permit and later for a long-term residence permit.</p>

Source: JRC elaboration based on country analysis.

Annex 6. Elements for an irregular migration dashboard

Sub-dimension of irregularity	Data and information	
Pathways into irregularity - Third-country nationals who do not fulfil conditions of entry		
Refused entry at the external border at border crossing points or internal if border checks are reintroduced	practice	Is an OTL issued in these circumstances?
	data source	Is there EU data? National data?
	value	How many persons were refused entry at the external border?
	persons who did not leave the country*	How many persons failed to leave the country after a refusal of entry?
Refused entry at the internal border	practice	Is an OTL issued in these circumstances?
	data source	Is there EU data? National data?
	value	How many persons were refused entry at the internal border?
	persons who did not leave the country*	How many persons failed to leave the country after a refusal of entry?
Refused entry in the proximity of the border	practice	Is an OTL issued in these circumstances?
	procedure	Is there a procedure to refuse entry in the proximity of the border?
	data source	Is there EU data? National data?
	value	How many persons were refused entry in the proximity of the border?
	persons who did not leave the country*	How many persons failed to leave the country after a refusal of entry?
Interceptions in connection with irregular border crossing	geographical considerations	Does the MS have an external sea or land border? Is this along any major irregular migration route?
	data source	Is there EU data? National data?
	value	How many persons were intercepted irregularly crossing the border?
Apprehension after irregular entry	practice	How does the MS verify if a person apprehended as irregular on its territory crossed the EU border irregularly?
	data source	Is there EU data? National data?
	value	How many people irregularly staying in the MS or ordered to leave entered the MS irregularly?
Analysis		Indicators
What is the ratio between refusals of entry at the internal border and at the external border?		- Comparison of refusals of entry at the internal and external border
To what extent do people refused entry fail to leave the country, potentially entering in the return system?		- Share of persons refused entry that do not leave the country
How significant is the irregular entry as pathway to irregularity?		- Share of the number of persons found to be irregularly present after an irregular entry over the total number of persons found to be irregularly present
How did the people in an irregular situation for irregular entry entered the country?		Comparison of the orders of magnitude of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - persons found to be irregularly present for irregular entry, - refusals of entry at the external border, - refusals of entry at the internal border, - interception for irregularly crossing the border
To what extent do persons identified as irregularly staying after having entered the country irregularly receive an OTL?		- Comparison of the orders of magnitude of persons found to be irregularly present after an irregular entry, and per-sons ordered to leave

Note* In principle, third-country nationals refused entry are prevented from entering the territory, hence from staying irregularly and eventually receiving an OTL. In practice, however, it may be that some people eventually enter the territory due to the impossibility to enforce the refusal of entry. No EU data is available to quantify this latter specific event

Pathways into irregularity - Loss of regular status		
Overstay when visa-exempt	practice	Which nationalities are visa-exempt? How do MS verify whether a person who is found to be irregularly present or is ordered to leave entered the EU as visa-exempt person?
	data source	Is there EU data? National data?
	value	How many irregularly staying persons or persons ordered to leave entered the country in the context of a visa-exemption agreement?
Overstay after a visa or residence permit	practice	How do MS verify whether a person who is irregularly staying or is ordered to leave entered the country regularly and overstayed the visa or permit?
		How is overstay defined in the national context?
	data source	Is there EU data? National data?
	value	How many irregularly staying persons or persons ordered to leave entered the country regularly and overstayed their visa/permit?
Overstay after unsuccessful asylum applications	practice	Are OTLs issued alongside asylum rejections? At which instance? By which authority?
	data source	Is there EU data? National data?
	value	How many persons found to be irregularly present or ordered to leave had an asylum rejection before?
Authorisation to stay revoked	practice	Under which conditions is an authorisation to stay revoked?
	data source	Is there EU data? National data?
	value	How many persons found to be irregularly present or ordered to leave had their authorisation to stay revoked?
Analysis		Indicators
How significant is the visa-exempt pathway to irregularity? And which countries does it involve?		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Share of visa exempt nationals among persons found to be irregularly present and ordered to leave - Top countries of citizenship/declared origin
How significant is the visa or permit overstay pathway into irregularity?		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Share of persons found to be irregularly present over-staying their visa and permit - Top countries of citizenship
How significant is the asylum rejection pathway into irregularity, and to what extent are asylum rejections followed by OTL?		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Share of OTL issued to rejected asylum applicants - Share of rejected asylum applicants at first and final instance receiving an OTL
Return processes		
Obligation to leave	practice	What is the national procedure that establishes an obligation to leave as per the Return Directive? Are there other procedures with similar aim? How long is an obligation to leave valid for? Do authorities systematically issue obligation to leave anytime a person is in an irregular situation?
	data source	Is there EU data? National data?
	value	How many persons are ordered to leave?
Postponement of the obligation to leave	practice - suspensive effect of appeals to the asylum or return decision	Which practices lead to a suspension of the OTL? (e.g. appeals to asylum or return procedure, legal or practical obstacles to return)
	practice - available temporary status during suspension	What are the consequences of the suspension of the OTL on the status of the person?
	data source	Is there EU data? National data?
	value	How many persons have a suspended OTL?
Evasion of enforcement (absconding)	practice	Are there any practices to prevent absconding? Are there any practices to identify whether an OTL refers to a person whose whereabouts are no longer known by the authorities?
	data source	Is there EU data? National data?
	value	How many persons abscond after receiving an OTL? How many OTL refers to absconded persons?

Analysis		Indicators
Which national practices are described by data on OTL?		-National procedures covered by the indicator on OTL
To what extent are OTL not enforceable due to suspension or absconding?		- Share of enforceable OTL - Share of suspended OTL - Share of OTL rereferring to absconded persons
Return processes		
Voluntary return	practice	How long is the granted period for voluntary departure? Is there counselling for voluntary and assisted return? Who is the target? Who is eligible for assistance in voluntary return? How is voluntary return monitored?
	data source	Is there EU data? National data?
	value	How many people return voluntarily? How many people returned under assisted voluntary return?
Forced return	practice	Which practice is in place to prevent people who failed to return voluntarily to abscond? Which practice is in place to guarantee an effective and fair implementation of forced returns?
	data source	Is there EU data? National data?
	value	How many people are returned forcibly?
Access to a residence permit	practice	Are there paths to residence permits available for persons in an irregular situation? What are the requirements to access?
	data source	Is there EU data? National data?
	value	How many get access to a residence permit after staying irregularly in the country, or being ordered to leave?
Analysis		Indicators
What is the most prevalent form of return from the country?		- Share of voluntary, assisted voluntary, and forced returns over total returns
How significant is return as a pathway out of irregularity?		- Share of persons returned over orders to leave/irregularly staying persons
How significant is the access to a residence permit as a pathway out of irregularity?		- Share of persons in an irregular situation/ordered to leave who accessed to a permit over orders to leave/irregularly staying persons

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